
D4.4 Linking next-generation EPCs to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

Task 4.3 Linking next-generation EPCs to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

WP4 Increasing the value of EPCs

Author: Nicole Hartl

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Accessible and reliable information on the energy efficiency of buildings and suitable renovation measures is essential for end users to make well-founded decisions regarding the renovation of their building. Building Renovation Passports (BRPs) and logbooks, mandated by the latest recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), aim to provide this crucial information. The integration of next-generation Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) with energy audits offers a more nuanced understanding of building energy performance, while logbooks facilitate continuous monitoring and documentation. BRPs ensure targeted renovation measures, fostering proactive energy management. However, their successful implementation requires clear policy measures and technical advancements to ensure interoperability, usability, and market acceptance.

As part of the crossCert project, an in-depth analysis of energy audit schemes in partner countries, alongside collaboration with H2020 projects, identified key policy and technical measures to enhance energy management in buildings.

1. Policy measures

a) **Harmonization with national and EU policies**

EPC frameworks must be aligned with the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), ISO/CEN standards, and national regulations to ensure consistency. Standardized methodologies should be established to facilitate cross-border comparability and effective policy integration.

b) **Strengthening data integration and sharing**

Secure and standardized data-sharing mechanisms need to be implemented to facilitate seamless exchange of information. Regulations should mandate the use of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and bidirectional data flows to enhance efficiency and interoperability.

a) **Ensuring financial incentives and regulatory compliance**

Financial incentives, such as renovation subsidies and tax benefits, should be directly linked to EPC-validated renovations to encourage investments in energy efficiency. Additionally, a mandatory update cycle for EPCs should be introduced to ensure that they accurately reflect energy audits and completed renovations.

b) **Strengthening public sector and stakeholder collaboration**

Stakeholder engagement must be improved through policy measures that enable better data access and cooperation. Public-private partnerships should be promoted to facilitate more effective implementation of EPC systems.

2. Technical measures

a) **Implement API-based integration and bidirectional data flows**

APIs should be developed to enable the seamless exchange of data between EPCs, energy audits, and digital logbooks, ensuring interoperability between different systems.

b) **Utilize blockchain for secure data management and machine learning for energy performance predictions**

Blockchain technology should be employed to enhance data security and transparency, while machine learning should be used to predict energy performance trends and optimize decision-making.

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- c) **Develop cloud-based solutions for scalable and cost-effective EPC integration**
Cloud-based platforms should be adopted to provide a scalable and cost-effective approach to EPC data management, allowing for greater flexibility and accessibility.
 - d) **Simplify digital tools for EPCs, BRPs, and logbooks**
Digital tools should be designed with user-friendly interfaces to enhance accessibility and usability for end users, ensuring that EPC data is easily interpretable and actionable.

3. Mixed measures (Policy & technical measures)

- a) **Promote training and awareness campaigns for homeowners, auditors, and real estate professionals**
Education initiatives should be developed as part of policy-driven strategies, with digital learning platforms supporting training efforts to increase awareness and adoption.
- b) **Mandate regular updates of EPCs based on energy audits and implemented renovations**
Regulatory requirements should be established to mandate regular updates of EPCs, with technical automation ensuring that these updates are accurate and efficient.

Close collaboration between energy consultants, building owners, public authorities and technical service providers is essential for the successful implementation of next-generation EPCs, logbooks and BRPs. Although coordinating these efforts can be challenging due to the varying systems and protocols used by different stakeholders, robust policy measures can ensure seamless integration.

The linkage of next-generation EPCs with energy audits, BRPs and logbooks presents a major opportunity to enhance building energy efficiency and support the EU's climate targets. Achieving this requires a combination of policy measures, technical innovations, financial incentives, and stakeholder collaboration. By implementing these recommendations, EPCs can become more effective, user-friendly, and impactful, accelerating the transition to a sustainable and energy-efficient building sector.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	6
1 LINKING THE SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON BUILDINGS	7
1.1 PURPOSES OF LINKING NEXT-GENERATION EPCs WITH ENERGY AUDITS, LOGBOOKS AND BRPs.....	7
1.2 SPECIFIC USE CASES FOR LINKING EPCs WITH ENERGY AUDITS, LOGBOOKS AND BRPs	7
1.3 CHALLENGES IN LINKING EPCs WITH ENERGY AUDITS, LOGBOOKS AND BRPs	9
2 ENERGY AUDITS IN PARTNER COUNTRIES	10
2.1 CHARACTERISTICS OF ENERGY AUDITS.....	10
2.2 OVERVIEW OF ENERGY AUDITS AND CONSULTATION SYSTEMS IN CROSSCERT PARTNER COUNTRIES:	11
2.2.1 Occasions for which an energy audit is mandatory	12
2.2.2 Obligation to issue an EPC as part of an energy audit	14
2.2.3 Obligation to do an energy audit as part of the EPC.....	14
2.2.4 Organisation of energy audits and implementation of standardised processes	15
2.2.5 Authorisation of sharing data	17
2.2.6 Digital availability of data.....	18
2.2.7 Stakeholders authorised for access to data from energy audits	19
2.2.8 Demand for energy advice	20
2.2.9 Sources of building information and linking energy audits with different databases.....	20
2.2.10 Smart meters as sources of information	22
2.2.11 Advancement of digitalisation in the partner countries.....	22
2.3 OUTLOOK ON THE DIGITALISATION OF DATA AND THE LINKING OF DATA SOURCES	24
3 READINESS OF NEXT-GENERATION EPC SCHEMES TO BE LINKED TO ENERGY AUDITS, LOGBOOKS AND BRPs	29
3.1 TARGET OF THE ANALYSIS OF NEXT-GENERATION EPC SCHEMES.....	29
3.2 BASIC FEATURES AND USE OF LOGBOOKS AND BRPs.....	29
3.2.1 Logbooks	29
3.2.2 Building Renovation Passports.....	29
3.2.3 Technical requirements for next-generation tools	30
3.3 NEXT-GENERATION EPC SCHEMES OF VARIOUS CROSSCERT SISTER PROJECTS.....	31
3.3.1 ALDREN - BRP	32
3.3.2 D ² EPC platform	35
3.3.3 E-DYCE platform	37
3.3.4 Smart Energy Performance Assessment Platform - SEPAP.....	40
3.3.5 iBRoad-Log & iBRoad-Plan	42
3.3.6 iBRoad2EPC.....	45
3.4 CONCLUSION – UTILISING FINDINGS FROM SISTER PROJECTS	49
4 RECOMMENDATIONS AND GUIDELINES	50
4.1 OVERCOMING ORGANISATIONAL AND DIGITALISATION BARRIERS.....	50
4.2 STRENGTHENING THE LINK BETWEEN EPCs, ENERGY AUDITS, LOGBOOKS, AND BRPs	51
4.3 CREATING A SUPPORTIVE FRAMEWORK FOR DATA SHARING AND RENOVATION INCENTIVES.....	51
4.4 IMPROVING USER EXPERIENCE AND MARKET ACCEPTANCE.....	51
4.5 TECHNICAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR EFFECTIVE INTEGRATION	52
4.6 THE ROLE OF THE RECOMMENDATIONS IN PROMOTING BUILDING ENERGY RENOVATION	52
5 CONCLUSIONS	54
6 REFERENCES	55

Introduction

The availability of easily accessible and understandable as well as graphically appealing and reliable information on buildings and suitable renovation measures to make them zero-energy buildings is vital for end users when deciding whether to rent or buy a building or carry out renovation measures. Building renovation passports (BRPs), required by the latest recast of the EPBD (Energy Performance of Buildings Directive), are intended to provide valuable information on measures to renovate a building towards zero-energy.

Storing clear and up-to-date information in one place makes it easier to plan and monitor a building the measures implemented and allows for an analysis of the current status of the building stock. Logbooks, which are required according to the latest EPBD recast, are intended to serve as such storage options.

Several H2020 projects have developed concepts for BRPs and logbooks. Furthermore, next-generation EPCs (Energy Performance Certificates) are of particular interest. Their concepts range from integrating consumption data, BIM (Building Information Modelling) and new indicators to linking EPC tools with energy audits, building logbooks and BRPs.

Linking next-generation EPCs to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs serves the multifaceted purpose of enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of energy management in buildings. The overarching goal is to create a **comprehensive and dynamic system that goes beyond the traditional static assessment** provided by conventional EPCs.

The activities carried out in WP 4 of crossCert concern the linking of new EPC schemes with energy audits, BRPs and logbooks.

As a starting point, a questionnaire for all project partners was developed to gather detailed information on the implementation of energy audits in their countries.

The next-generation EPC schemes were assessed concerning their readiness to be linked to the digital tools mentioned above – energy audits, BRPs and logbooks. Therefore, the experience gained from the cross-testing (task 2.3) also provided insight into the new digital tools and their possible use and integration into EPC schemes. The result is a set of recommendations and guidelines for the integration of all these tools to promote building energy renovation.

1 Linking the sources of information on buildings

1.1 Purposes of linking next-generation EPCs with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

A lot of information about a building may already exist, coming from energy audits, logbooks and BRPs. Using this information – in a first stage for the EPC and in a second stage for long-term purposes such as renovation strategies and monitoring – brings added value to building owners, property managers, EPC issuers and auditors. Furthermore, energy agencies, researchers, public authorities and financial providers can benefit from such a connection.

Linking next-generation EPCs to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs serves the multifaceted purpose of enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of energy management in buildings. The overarching goal is to create a comprehensive and dynamic system that goes beyond the traditional static assessment provided by conventional EPCs.

The main purpose is to leverage the synergies between EPCs and energy audits for a more nuanced understanding of a building's energy performance. While EPCs provide a baseline assessment, energy audits delve deeper into the operational aspects and identify specific areas for improvement. Linking these two components allows for a more holistic evaluation, enabling tailored recommendations for energy efficiency measures.

Furthermore, the integration with digital logbooks contributes to a continuous monitoring and documentation of a building's energy consumption and all renovations carried out. When connected to next-generation EPCs, this real-time data facilitates dynamic updates, ensuring that the certificate reflects the most current and accurate information. Logbooks also play a crucial role in providing a historical context that offers insights into the effectiveness of past energy efficiency interventions.

BRPs are seamlessly incorporated into this integrated system, providing a structured roadmap for implementing energy-efficient measures identified through energy audits. This ensures that the weaknesses identified in the EPCs are fed into the renovation plans, creating a feedback loop that guides targeted and prioritised renovation actions.

The central goal of this integrated approach is to promote proactive energy management. By facilitating continuous monitoring, regular updates and the incorporation of customised recommendations, the system encourages building owners and stakeholders to adopt a forward-thinking mindset. Ultimately, the aim is to promote sustainable improvements in energy efficiency, reduce environmental impact and focus on broader sustainability objectives.

In summary, linking next-generation EPCs with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs aims to overcome the limitations of traditional energy certification processes. The goal is to create a dynamic, data-driven ecosystem that empowers stakeholders with actionable insights, promotes informed decision-making and fosters a continuous cycle of building energy performance improvement.

This paper examines the promising integration of next-generation EPCs with established tools such as energy consultations, digital logbooks and comprehensive renovation roadmaps.

1.2 Specific use cases for linking EPCs with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

Specific use cases for linking EPCs with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs contribute to a more comprehensive and effective approach to the energy management of buildings. The following part highlights some specific scenarios in which this integration can prove beneficial:

Targeted energy efficiency recommendations: Energy audits identify specific areas of inefficiency in a building. Linking these audit results with EPCs enables the generation of targeted and prioritised recommendations in the certificate, providing actionable insights for building owners to improve energy performance.

Continuous monitoring and dynamic updates: Regular updates on energy consumption and renovations carried out are recorded in a digital logbook. Integrating logbook data into EPCs allows for dynamic updates to ensure they reflect the most up-to-date information. This real-time monitoring contributes to a more accurate representation of the building's energy efficiency.

Historical performance analysis: Logbooks keep records of energy consumption and renovation activities. By linking logbook data with EPCs, building owners can analyse historical performance trends. This facilitates a retrospective evaluation of the effectiveness of past energy efficiency measures and provides information for future decisions.

Informed planning of building renovations: BRPs outline a structured roadmap for the renovation of buildings. The weaknesses identified in EPCs are directly introduced into the BRPs, ensuring that the renovation plans are aligned with the specific challenges regarding the building's energy performance. This integration streamlines the implementation of targeted energy efficiency measures.

Lifecycle assessment and long-term planning: EPCs provide a snapshot of current energy performance. Linking EPCs with logbooks and BRPs allows for a comprehensive life cycle assessment. This integration facilitates long-term planning by considering historical data, current performance and future renovation strategies.

Compliance tracking and reporting: Regulatory requirements mandate periodic energy audits and certification updates. By linking audit results and certification updates with EPCs, the system can automatically track and report on compliance with regulatory standards. This ensures that building owners stay in line with energy efficiency regulations.

Enhanced communication and stakeholder collaboration: Various stakeholders, including energy consultants, building owners and renovation contractors, collaborate on energy management initiatives. Platforms that facilitate the integration can enhance their communication by providing them with a centralised space to access and contribute to relevant data. This collaborative environment streamlines the decision-making and implementation processes.

These use cases highlight the tangible benefits of linking EPCs with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs. The synergy between these components contributes to a more nuanced and adaptive approach to building energy management, ultimately fostering sustainable improvements in energy efficiency.

Public authorities can benefit significantly from linking EPCs with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs. It provides a robust framework for informed decision-making, effective policy implementation and enhanced monitoring. Here are some specific use cases for public authorities:

Policy compliance and regulation enforcement: Regulatory frameworks require buildings to undergo energy audits and maintain updated EPCs. By linking energy audits and EPCs, public authorities can easily track and enforce compliance with energy efficiency regulations. Automated systems can provide real-time updates, ensuring that buildings adhere to mandated standards.

Data-driven policy development: Authorities aim to formulate evidence-based energy efficiency policies. Access to integrated data allows them to analyse trends in energy consumption, renovation activities and the effectiveness of implemented measures. This data-driven approach informs the development of targeted and impactful energy efficiency policies.

Monitoring and benchmarking building performance: Authorities want to monitor and benchmark the energy performance of public buildings. Linking EPCs, energy audits and logbooks facilitates continuous monitoring of the performance of public buildings. Benchmarking against established standards becomes more accurate, enabling authorities to identify underperforming buildings and prioritise interventions.

Efficient allocation of resources: Limited resources require efficient allocation for energy efficiency initiatives. Using integrated data, authorities can identify buildings with high potential for energy savings. This enables a strategic allocation of resources that directs investments and incentives to where they are most needed and can have the greatest impact.

Streamlined reporting and documentation: Authorities must compile and report on the energy performance of public buildings. An automation in linking EPCs, logbooks and BRPs streamlines this process. Public authorities can generate comprehensive reports with accurate and up-to-date information, demonstrating transparency and compliance with energy efficiency goals.

Identification of priority buildings for renovation: The integration of data helps to identify buildings with suboptimal energy performance through EPCs and audits. Public authorities can use this information to prioritise buildings for targeted renovation efforts and thus maximise the impact of energy efficiency measures.

Facilitation of stakeholder collaboration: Multiple stakeholders, such as energy consultants and building owners, are involved in energy management initiatives. Platforms supporting the integration provide them with a collaborative environment. Public authorities can facilitate communication and coordination between the various parties, fostering a more coherent approach to energy efficiency projects.

Continuous improvement of energy policies: Authorities aim to adapt and enhance energy policies based on evolving data. Integrated data allows public authorities to assess the effectiveness of existing energy policies. By identifying trends and success factors, authorities can iteratively improve policies for sustained and impactful outcomes.

In summary, linking EPCs with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs empowers public authorities with comprehensive data for effective policy development, monitoring and resource allocation. This integrated approach supports the overarching goal of improving energy efficiency in public buildings and contributes to broader sustainability objectives.

1.3 Challenges in linking EPCs with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

Linking energy certificates, energy consultations, logbooks and Building Renovation Passports poses several challenges, including technical, organisational and legal aspects:

Data privacy and security: The integration involves the exchange and linking of sensitive data, including energy consumption, renovation plans and personal information of building owners. Ensuring compliance with data protection regulations and implementing secure data transmission and storage mechanisms is crucial.

Interoperability and standardisation: The diversity of systems and platforms used for energy certificates, consultations, logbooks and renovation passports can lead to interoperability issues. Developing uniform standards is critical to facilitate smooth data exchange across different systems.

Diversity of building types and age classes: Buildings vary significantly in types, age classes and technical specifications. The challenge is to create flexible solutions applicable to a variety of buildings while still providing meaningful information.

Stakeholder coordination: Linking requires close collaboration among various stakeholders, including energy consultants, building owners, authorities and technical service providers. Coordinating them can be challenging, especially when different parties use different systems and protocols.

Timeliness of data: To derive real benefits, data must be updated in real-time. It is crucial to ensure that information on energy consumption and renovation measures is regularly entered and updated, particularly in logbooks and renovation passports.

Financing and resources: The implementation and maintenance of integrated systems require financial resources and technical support. The challenge is to ensure that both public and private entities can provide the necessary funds for the introduction and maintenance of these systems.

Awareness and training: Stakeholders need to be aware of the benefits and functionality of integrated systems. The challenge is to develop training programmes and awareness campaigns to ensure that all parties understand and can utilise the integration.

Legal framework: Legal issues may arise, particularly regarding data protection, liability and legal requirements for the creation of energy certificates and renovation passports. Harmonising legal frameworks at national and European level can be challenging.

Technological developments: The rapid evolution of new technologies can be a challenge, especially if established systems rely on outdated technologies. Flexibility in adapting to technological developments is crucial.

Addressing these challenges requires a coordinated effort from governments, businesses, research institutions and other stakeholders. However, comprehensive and standardised integration can offer significant benefits for building efficiency and sustainable energy management.

2 Energy audits in partner countries

Prior to assessing the readiness of next-generation EPC schemes to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and building renovation passports, we have to understand energy audit schemes, processes and data availability, especially digital availability. For this purpose a survey was carried out among the crossCert partner countries.

2.1 Characteristics of energy audits

The crossCert partner countries have differing systems for energy audits and energy advice for residential and commercial buildings. These systems vary in terms of their structure, financing, processes, data gathering, data storage and mandatory measures. A common feature is the provision of energy advice by both government bodies and independent energy agencies.

The energy consultations focus on various aspects, including improving building insulation, heating systems, water heating and electricity consumption and promoting renewable energies etc. The recommendations are aimed at increasing energy efficiency and promoting the use of sustainable energy.

The structure and availability of advice varies considerably. Some countries offer government-subsidised advice, which is generally free of charge. Others rely on fee-based services, with costs varying according to the target group and government subsidy programme.

In general, prior information about the building in question is often required online to facilitate the consultation process. The use of online platforms and web-based applications to manage advisory services is also widespread.

Some countries have introduced mandatory energy audits and energy performance certificates for certain categories of buildings.

In addition, web-based tools such as applications for managing energy consulting services are used in some cases. These facilitate the efficient organisation of customer data, resources and costs for energy agencies.

The following overview highlights the diversity of approaches across the partner countries, but also emphasises common goals such as promoting energy efficiency, the use of renewable energy and the provision of energy advice services for different types of buildings.

2.2 Overview of energy audits and consultation systems in crossCert partner countries:

The following part gives an overview of the characteristics of energy audits in the crossCert partner countries.

1. Austria:

- Energy advice for residential buildings and non-residential buildings provided by energy agencies of federal states
- Online submission of information required in advance in some federal states
- Consultation reports are written
- Consultation also available by phone (free of charge, 30 minutes)
- On-site visits may incur small costs
- ZEUS (Central EPC environment), a web-based database, offers a logbook for showing EPCs, consultancy protocols, renovation passports, energy consumption and gains (by integrating meters), realised renovation measures, for applying for funding and for managing energy consulting services. Additional tools can be implemented. These tools or parts of these tools are used in some federal states. Others probably will follow in the future.

2. Bulgaria:

- Energy advice is regulated by the Energy Efficiency Act and related ordinances.
- Energy audits are mandatory for public buildings >250 m².
- Audits performed by accredited consultants; accreditation levels based on qualifications
- Results presented in a free text report and a standardised Excel summary
- The EPC is also a mandatory document to be issued after the completion of an energy audit.
- Energy performance certificate required for property transactions
- Recommended energy saving measures are described in the report and in the Excel summary and are also indicated briefly in the EPC.
- There are random checks of EPCs conducted by officials of SEDA (Sustainable Energy Development Agency). These checks do not only cover the EPC but also the energy audit report and the Excel summary.

3. Denmark:

- No mandatory energy audit for building owners
- EPC required for selling, renting or financing
- Voluntary energy audits available
- Energy label (EPC) reveals energy consumption and suggests improvements
- Large companies are obligated to conduct an energy audit every four years

4. Spain:

- Energy audits are comprehensive studies of technical and economic aspects
- Use of specialised measuring devices, including thermographic cameras and lux meters
- Energy audit planning includes the establishing of specifications and gathering prior information
- Final report includes recommendations for improving energy performance

5. Greece:

- Energy audits integrated into the EPC scheme
- EPCs issued by engineers after visiting the building and performing necessary calculations
- Recommendations for energy efficiency improvements are mandatory

6. Croatia:

- Energy audits and certification by certified persons authorised by the Ministry
- Energy performance certificate issued after the audit
- Ministry officials conduct random checks on EPCs

7. Malta

Energy audits are generally only carried out for business companies only (both large companies and SMEs as described in the first question of the questionnaire). For the residential sector, they are very rarely requested and carried out and there is no scheme to promote the uptake of such services across the domestic sector. In the rare case that a household wishes to have an energy audit carried out, they are free to contact any expert or consultancy firm and there is no regulation on how such audits are carried out. Furthermore, such audits would not be collected by any central authority. There is no regulation/data/templates for such audits in Malta and therefore it is not possible to answer the questionnaire regarding energy audits focused primarily on the residential sector.

8. Poland

- EPCs mandatory for energy audits
- Decentralised organisation
- Voluntary tools for energy advice in Word or Excel format to ease the process for energy advisors

9. Slovenia:

- Energy audits cover public buildings, large companies, SMEs and residential buildings.
- Obligatory energy audits for public buildings during deep renovations and for large companies every four years
- Energy advice provided by national energy advisory networks and local energy agencies, free-market energy service

10. United Kingdom:

- Energy Performance Reports (EPR) produced for the ECO4 scheme
- Grants provided for energy-efficient upgrades to homes
- Home surveys conducted and EPR used to determine improvement measures
- Aimed at increasing energy efficiency and reducing fuel poverty and energy costs

The diversity of energy audit and consultation systems in the partner countries, as shown in this overview, demonstrates the importance of tailored approaches to meet specific national goals and regulations.

2.2.1 Occasions for which an energy audit is mandatory

Energy audits are, especially for older buildings, **a vital source of current information about a building** and a suitable occasion to gather documents about it. **The more often energy consultations are carried out, the more opportunities there are to obtain up-to-date information about a specific building.** The potential for the frequency of energy consultations has an effect on the possibilities for obtaining up-to-date information and, for example, using a next-generation EPC tool for entering data, filling in a logbook or creating a BRP. The following figure shows the share of different obligations of an energy audit.

Figure 1: Occasions in which an energy audit is mandatory - total

For single renovation measures, an energy audit is (partly) mandatory in two countries. If a building owner applies for subsidies an energy audit is mandatory in most countries.

The category “**Other**” indicates, that the obligation of carrying out an energy audit is linked to certain conditions. In Croatia, energy audits are mandatory when a building (or parts of it) larger than 50 m² is sold or rented, as well as for new buildings and public buildings with a floor area larger than 250 m². In Greece, energy audits are required for issuing an EPC and therefore mandatory for selling or renting any building or building unit and also for newly constructed buildings. In Slovenia, energy audits are mandatory for comprehensive renovations only when public (co)financing is requested and for starting a PPP (energy performance contract) process for public buildings.

The following figure shows the obligation to conduct energy audits in each of the project partner countries. This element indicates the possible amount of energy consultations. It can be assumed that in countries where energy audits are voluntary, fewer data sets are available for linking.

Figure 2: Occasions in which an energy audit is mandatory, listed for each crossCert partner country

As shown in the figure, voluntary energy audits can be commissioned in every country. In most countries, energy audits are mandatory for the application for subsidies. In two countries, an energy audit is mandatory for the building permission of single renovation measures. In Austria, this differs depending on the federal states (Bundesländer). When applying for state funding in Austria, both the consultancy protocol and an EPC are valid.

In Denmark, energy audits are not mandatory for large renovations, but they are highly beneficial and often integrated into the renovation process. The Danish Building Regulations require that major renovations meet specific energy performance standards, and energy audits are a practical tool for assessing and ensuring compliance with these requirements.

2.2.2 Obligation to issue an EPC as part of an energy audit

A solid and reliable EPC is the basis for recommending suitable renovation measures. Therefore calculating an EPC in combination with an energy audit serves as a sound source of information for the end user. As shown in the figure below, an EPC is a mandatory part of an energy audit in 33 % of the partner countries, whereas there is no such obligation in the majority of the countries.

Figure 3: Obligation to create an EPC as part of an energy audit

2.2.3 Obligation to do an energy audit as part of the EPC

When issuing an EPC, an on-site visit and an accompanying energy audit are advisable – especially for older existing buildings. In this way, the condition of the building can be examined, as the actual plans and physics may be different from those shown on the (older) plans. In 33 % of the countries an energy audit is part of issuing an EPC, as the following figure shows.

Figure 4: Obligation to undertake an energy audit as part of an EPC

If a building is sold or rented and thus an EPC is necessary, the actual state of the building can be validated at this point and the logbook can be updated.

2.2.4 Organisation of energy audits and implementation of standardised processes

The organisation of energy audits – centralised or decentralised – has an effect on the simplicity and effectiveness of introducing and implementing reporting standards. This relates to the software or database in use, data formats, linkages, necessary data to be gathered during the energy audit and organisational processes. As the following figure shows, energy audits are mainly organised in a decentralised way. That means, that energy audits are organised by different agencies, but also that there are no coordinated organisational processes when building owners or tenants commission a service provider by themselves.

Figure 5: Organisation of energy audits

A decentralised organisation of energy audits makes it difficult to implement a standardised process, as national guidelines or standards would have to be published, e.g. in a regulation, which is time-

consuming and more complex than working out a standardised process within one organisation in charge.

Nevertheless, a standardisation is vital for the simple use of data from energy audits and is therefore recommended for introduction in the countries.

The countries with a central organisation of energy audits (Austria and United Kingdom) offer mandatory templates for the collection of data and the required results. In these cases a software is used to fill in data. Linking it to other data bases like EPC data bases or logbooks and BRPs is technically feasible.

The following table shows the obligation for using tools for energy advice and their format in the partner countries with a **decentralised** organisation.

	Bulgaria	Croatia	Denmark	Greece	Poland	Slovenia	Spain
Mandatory tool		x		x			
Voluntary tool	x				x	x	
Format	Software	Database	Hub (pilot stage)	Software	Word, Excel	PDF	Database

Table 1: Obligations for the use of tools for energy advice and their formats

Using a hub is the ideal format, as different sources of information are already linked to each other. With some effort, a software program or a database can be linked to other sources of information. Therefore, these two possibilities are coloured green. Filling in a Word or Excel file or even only having a PDF document available increases the effort or prevents the possibility for using data out of these documents. However, the documents could at least be saved in a logbook. Therefore, these formats are coloured orange.

Good-practice example of making data digitally available despite decentralised organisation:

In Croatia, despite the decentralised organisation of energy audits, there are mandatory tools and templates to be used, which are based on special software. Thus, linking data is technically viable.

In Poland and Slovenia, voluntary tools are available (Word and PDF documents, in Poland also Excel documents). There is potential to digitalise information in a way that it can be evaluated – e.g. in databases, software programs, web applications, etc.

In Denmark and Spain, there is no tool that can be used as a template for data collection in energy audits.

In Denmark, digitalisation will play an increasingly important role in the next few years. It is worth mentioning an ongoing test project under the Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Supply (since 2021). This project is testing a Building Hub which is aimed at promoting the green transition of buildings by creating an overview of the efficiency opportunities that lie in the use of data and digitalisation.

Good-practice example of sharing data:

The Building Hub in Denmark, a pilot project at the moment, is a digital platform that provides access to data about buildings and their energy consumption. It collects and displays data on energy consumption in buildings, data on the energy characteristics of buildings from The Central Register of Buildings and Dwellings (BBR), the energy labelling database (EPC) and weather stations.

The project will provide experience on how improved access to data on buildings and energy consumption can be used in the work on the green transition and energy efficiency of buildings in Denmark. Further information is not yet available at the time of writing.

The monitoring and implementation of these plans could be linked with BRPs.

2.2.5 Authorisation of sharing data

The technical availability of data and their format is one aspect of the feasibility and benefit of sharing and linking data. The authorisation of sharing data is another important aspect. The figure below shows, that only in Denmark different authorities are allowed to share data on buildings, as the Danish Energy Agency administrates a public EPC database as well as the Hub, which is in the pilot phase, thus enabling the following stakeholders to pursue different strategies:

- Building owners to get access to data that provide a better basis for planning energy efficiency improvements and energy optimisation in buildings
- Businesses to get a better data basis that they can use to target energy efficiency offers or 'train' digital models (which is not very welcome in some countries)
- Authorities to get a stronger basis for creating better framework conditions for energy efficiency in public buildings and society in general.

Figure 6: Authorisation to share data

On the other side of the scale is Poland, where sharing data on buildings is not allowed at the moment.

In between lies the majority of countries that share data for certain purposes or in certain cases.

Good-practice example of sharing data and creating logbooks and BRPs:

In Austria, Salzburg is the leading federal state when it comes to the digitalisation and linking of building data. In future, the other federal states will also use this system. In Salzburg, the EPC database is connected to the so-called internet database ZEUS (Central EPC environment), which contains energy advice data and reports, as well as to the funding authority. Inspection reports and smart meters can also be integrated. In addition, the building owner can give access to the data to selected professionals, for example. All these systems are realised by one service provider. Thus, the technical interfaces are easy to implement.

In Bulgaria, anyone can access the public data in the national database of the audited buildings, but additional data cannot be presented without the consent of the building owner.

In Croatia, most data is not publicly available. Data could be shared with the funding authority, ESCOs (Energy Service Companies) and between professionals working on a construction/renovation of the building, etc.

In Greece, requests for building data are reviewed on a case by case basis by the Ministry of Energy, resulting in significant delays. In the case of requests for the purpose of research, only aggregated/anonymised data are shared.

In Slovenia, data from energy audits of the public sector is not protected, but it is for the private sector. Municipalities may enable public access to an energy audit in case of the “publication of a public call for expressions of interest from promoters for the implementation of a project in the form of a public-private partnership”.

In Spain, there is a Ministerial Energy Audits database, but registered data is not public. Only cadastral and EPC data are available about buildings. Information provided is accessible by Spanish Public Administration.

In Denmark, all EPCs are publicly available in a central database. This database contains detailed information on the energy performance of buildings, including energy ratings, recommendations for energy improvements, and other relevant data. The EPC Database is publicly accessible, allowing users to search for and obtain information about the energy performance of specific buildings.

Denmark has implemented a widespread rollout of smart meters to enhance energy management and efficiency. Smart meters provide detailed data on energy consumption, which can be used for various purposes, including billing, energy efficiency analysis, and demand response programs. Access to smart meter data is well-regulated and designed to benefit consumers, energy suppliers, grid operators, and third-party service providers. The regulatory framework ensures data privacy and security while promoting the use of smart meter data to enhance energy efficiency and grid management.

2.2.6 Digital availability of data

If digital information is available, there is a good chance that it can be linked and therefore be used for specific use-cases. This table shows the digital availability of data in the partner countries to show the current technical feasibility of linking data.

	Austria	Bulgaria	Croatia	Denmark	Greece	Poland	Slovenia	Spain	United Kingdom
Energy audit data available in database or software	x	x	x	x	x				x
EPC data available in database or software	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	(xls)
Inspection report available in database	x		x	x			x	x	
Land register available in database	x	x	x	x	x		x		x
National building cadastre available in database	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	

Table 2: Digital availability of different data in crossCert partner countries

In Austria, Croatia and Denmark, energy audit data, EPC data, inspection reports, the land register and the national building cadastre are digitally available, which shows that the technical possibility of linking the different databases to each other is basically given. Such linking is important for various kinds of evaluations. For example:

In Austria, specifically in the federal state of Salzburg, these databases are already linked. The other federal states will follow over time. At the moment, many of them still use Word or Excel files, so there is a lot of potential for linking data.

In Denmark, the pilot project Hub mentioned above is a digital platform that provides access to data about buildings and their energy consumption.

In Croatia, a lot of digital tools exist to manage building data. These tools are mainly web-based services. The technical feasibility is given.

In Bulgaria, all data except the inspection report is available. At the moment, the data is not linked with other databases.

In Greece, there is a connection between the databases:

A RESTful web service allows to provide data to

- Funding database (EPC validation and calculation results)
- Building logbook (EPC validation) and
- Tax department (EPC validation for rented buildings).

Data is also gathered from the Land registry (geolocation data).

In Poland, there is the EPC database, but results of energy audits are not digitally available in a database or software program, so there is no connection.

In Slovenia, data is digitally available, except for information from energy audits. A connection as well as the authorisation to share data are still to be implemented.

In Spain, building owners receive a written report. This information is not digitally available and thus cannot be linked to other sources of information.

In the United Kingdom, results from energy audits are entered to a software program. Linking to other sources of information has not yet been implemented.

2.2.7 Stakeholders authorised for access to data from energy audits

Providing different stakeholders with access to different kinds of information makes it easier to plan and monitor activities.

The following table shows who has access to the stored data specifically from **energy audits**:

	Austria	Bulgaria	Croatia	Denmark	Greece	Poland	Slovenia	Spain	United Kingdom
Authorities	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	
Energy advisors	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
Building owners	x	x		x		x	x		
Building users		x		x					
General public		x							
Not specified									x

Table3: Stakeholders authorised for access to data from energy audits

In all countries except for Slovenia and the United Kingdom, authorities have access to data from energy audits. Thus, this data can be taken into account for an analysis of the building stock and targeted policy strategies.

In Bulgaria, the entire energy audit documentation is available to building owners and energy advisors, but they do not have access to the national database of audited buildings (NDAB).

In Greece the building owner receives only the EPC in hardcopy or PDF.

In all countries, of course, the building owner receives the results of the energy audit, but in some countries there is no access to further information or digital tools to see updated information afterwards.

2.2.8 Demand for energy advice

The higher the demand for energy advice, the more opportunities there are to collect current data of a building and to introduce new features and tools such as next-generation EPCs, logbooks or BRPs.

Figure 7: Demand for energy advice

In 62 % of the crossCert partner countries (Austria, Croatia, Denmark, Poland and Slovenia) there is a high demand for energy advice and thus a high potential for available data, which realistically represents the building and its technical devices.

In Bulgaria, the demand for energy advice is low because owners do not know enough about this service and its potential benefits and it is quite expensive for most people, especially in the residential sector.

In Greece, energy audits are part of the EPC and therefore the demand for extra energy advice is low.

In Spain, there is a high demand for advice on public subsidies. There is a great potential in increasing people's interest in building energy performance.

2.2.9 Sources of building information and linking energy audits with different databases

Reporting measures carried out in a building is a prerequisite for the availability of up-to-date data. It is therefore advisable to implement mandatory reporting procedures – for single refurbishment measures and major renovations as well as for the replacement of heating systems. This information should be linked to the logbook and the BRP.

The following table shows the current state in the partner countries regarding the necessity of building permits or reporting requirements for refurbishment measures or the replacement of heating systems. These documents are potential sources of information. Another source is the funding database.

However, in these cases only subsidised measures are listed. An option to record every measure would be to regulate the reporting of all renovations or replacements of heating systems for measures which are not funded.

A further source of information is the EPC database¹. Although EPC databases have been set up in almost all partner countries, only in some cases they are linked – the same applies to the land register.

In the following table the colouring has the following meaning:

Green	Advanced stage Measures have to be reported or applied for in a building permit, databases are linked.
Orange	Existing potential to use data Database existing, with potential to be linked.
Red	High improvement potential No record of measures, no database available

Table 4: Explanation of colouring of table 5

	Any retrofitting or replacement	Major renovations	Change of heating system	Linkage to funding database	Linkage to EPC database	Land register
Austria	Reporting not mandatory	Building permit	Report	Yes	Yes	Yes
Bulgaria	Building permit	Building permit	Report	No, but database existing	No, but database existing	No, but database existing
Croatia	Reporting not mandatory	Report	Report		No, but database existing	No, but database existing
Denmark	Report	Report	Building permit		Yes	Yes
Greece	Building permit	Building permit	Reporting not mandatory	Yes	No, but database existing	Yes
Malta	Reporting not mandatory	Building permit	Reporting not mandatory		Reporting not mandatory	Reporting not mandatory
Poland	Reporting not mandatory	Building permit	Report		No, but database existing	Reporting not mandatory
Slovenia	Reporting not mandatory	Reporting not mandatory	Reporting not mandatory		No, but database existing	No, but database existing
Spain	Building permit	Reporting not mandatory	Reporting not mandatory		No, but database existing	No, but database existing
United Kingdom	Building permit	Building permit	Reporting not mandatory			

¹ In Bulgaria energy audits and EPCs are always combined and there is only one joint database.

Table 5: Sources of building information and linking of energy audits to different databases

In Greece, Malta, Slovenia, Spain and the United Kingdom, there is no obligation to report the replacement of the heating system.

In Austria, Croatia, Malta, Poland and Slovenia, single renovation measures do not have to be reported or even permitted.

If renovation measures are subsidised, this information is available in the funding database, which can also be linked to the building logbook and the building renovation passport, but as we can see in Figure 6, the permission to share data between different authorities still needs to be developed.

There are probably no technical barriers to linking databases as data there is digitally available.

2.2.10 Smart meters as sources of information

Smart meters are a suitable source of information for building logbooks to show the actual consumption of electricity, heat, water or gas.

In most partner countries smart meters for electricity are partly installed, but the data cannot yet be used on a broad scale due to data protection rules and missing linkages to appropriate web services (e.g. logbooks).

Good-practice example of using smart meter data:

In Austria, the building owner can permit the transfer of smart meter data to the ZEUS database, which serves as a logbook.

In Croatia, smart meter data is linked to the EPC database.

In the UK, the project “Smart meter energy data repository”, which is looking into creating such repository, is currently in progress.

2.2.11 Advancement of digitalisation in the partner countries

The project partners were asked to rate the advancement of their country in digitalising building information and setting up a BRP and a logbook. The following figures show the results of the qualitative estimations.

Figure 8: Advancement in digitalising available building information – estimation by the project partners

Figure 9: Advancement in setting up a building renovation roadmap - estimation by the project partners

Figure 10: Advancement in setting up a digital logbook - estimation by the project partners

The majority of the crossCert partner countries are rather not advanced in digitalising building information and setting up BRPs and logbooks.

In general, available data is not being linked and there are considerable data protection and legal issues as well as a lack of willingness to link different sources of information.

Nevertheless, there are some interesting examples of good practice in these fields and developments and engagement are ongoing.

Recent next-generation EPC projects have created tools to support the development and implementation of BRPs and building logbooks and to promote the linkage of different information sources. These results of these projects will help partner countries to set up the conditions for linking the different tools and databases.

The following chapter will shed light on next-generation EPC schemes, BRPs and logbooks developed in crossCert sister projects. The tools and schemes are analysed regarding their readiness to be linked to energy audits, BRPs and logbooks.

2.3 Outlook on the digitalisation of data and the linking of data sources

Austria

In Austria, the federal state of Salzburg is leading in the digitalisation of available building data and setting up and implementing a BRP and logbooks. In this case, the ZEUS database (building logbook) shows the available EPCs of the building, the energy audit report (input via a short version of the EPC calculation program), the renovation passport, which includes measures (including U-values) to refurbish the building to a NZEB, the measures implemented and energy accounting via smart meter data (anyone can register for free on this web service, for buildings larger than 1.000 m² smart meter data must be reported once a day).

These linkages enable the building owners to see all relevant information about their building in one web application, in addition, data like the actual energy consumption over time, PV gains, etc. are shown in graphs. Access to this data can be granted by the building owner to anyone.

This approach could be adopted by all Austrian federal states. They will follow as soon as the obligation is defined in the OIB Guideline 6. For the time being, most federal states use lists and Word documents as well as handwritten notes to produce energy audit reports. Furthermore, the reports are not saved in a database.

In Lower Austria, the consultation report is currently being digitalised so that its information can automatically be stored in the internet database ZEUS. Follow-up activities in the future are necessary to set values for evaluation and analysis, as a support for the energy agencies and authorities of the provinces.

In Vorarlberg, the report is printed on paper, and will remain so, as the energy consultants prefer to have some pages to hand to make notes and possibly drawings. There is a certain reluctant attitude to use digital tools.

Filling in a printed document and transferring the data to the database or an online tool bears two problems: Firstly, it is more time-consuming for the energy advisor and secondly, it is a source of error. The responsible authority (Energieinstitut Vorarlberg) is monitoring developments related to online questionnaires and the ZEUS database to make data digitally available in the distant future.

The recommendation is to introduce and use the ZEUS database in all Austrian federal states, to the same extent as it is done in Salzburg, and to support the implementation with a sound marketing campaign to inform building owners and users about the benefits of these tools.

Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, a copy of all documents presenting the energy audit results is electronically sent to SEDA (Sustainable Energy Development Agency). SEDA oversees the quality of the documentation and transfers the data to the public national database of audited buildings.

For individual funding programs targeting energy efficiency in buildings, applicants must also submit an energy audit of their building. This audit recommends and evaluates the measures to be implemented and funded by the respective program.

Summarized data from all energy audits is publicly available in the national energy audit database and accessible to anyone interested. However, the full documentation from the energy audit for a specific building is only available to SEDA, the energy auditor who conducted the audit, and the building owner.

Croatia

There are many databases (e.g. digital energy certificates, digital energy audit reports) in Croatia and their integration has started in the last six to eight years. However, the integration of all databases and their availability to the general public are still a long way off. Although many documents have been digitalised, a lot of necessary documentation is missing or only available in the software of various companies.

The data for all buildings audited since 2017 has already been digitalised but it is only available to professionals. With the integration of IEC (eCertificates) into the ISPU Geoportal, which contains more information than in the current state, this information would be available to the general public for each building they select on the map.

The use of BIM for this activity in the framework of international projects (e.g. Timepac) was discussed. A standardised software program or web application to fill in necessary data during an energy audit and data available in one database would be helpful.

Denmark

The EPBD requirement will be considered over the next one to two years. Digitalisation will play an increasingly important role. A new National Strategy for Digitalisation 2022-2026 was adopted by the Danish Government in May 2022 based on nine visions that set the direction for digital solutions regarding concrete problems in society and create value for citizens and businesses. One of these visions is "Acceleration of the green transition through digital solutions", which aims to combine various data from different sectors and databases, to improve the quality of digital EPCs and to provide recommendations. Furthermore, it could be pivotal for coordinating the measures included in the EPBD recast.

As already mentioned in this report, there is an ongoing test project under the Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Supply (since 2021). This project is testing a Building Hub which is aimed at promoting the green transition of buildings by creating an overview of the efficiency opportunities that lie in the use of data and digitalisation.

The Building Hub is a digital platform that provides access to data about buildings and their energy consumption. It collects and displays data on energy consumption in buildings, data on the energy characteristics of buildings from The Central Register of Buildings and Dwellings (BBR), the energy labelling database (EPC) and weather stations. The following data sources can be used and combined:

- Aggregated electricity consumption data on an hourly basis
- Aggregated district heating consumption data on an hourly basis
- Data from the Danish Energy Agency's energy labelling database, including background data for the energy labels
- Data from DMI (Danish Meteorological Institute) weather stations on local weather conditions
- Data from BBR (Central Register of Buildings Dwelling), including the buildings' use, areas, physical characteristics, etc.

The overall purpose is:

- Building owners get access to data that provides a better basis for planning energy efficiency improvements and energy optimisation in buildings.
- Businesses get a better data basis they can use to target energy efficiency offers or 'train' digital models.
- Authorities get a stronger basis for creating better framework conditions for energy efficiency in public buildings and society in general.

The project will provide experience on how improved access to data on building and energy consumption can be used in the work on the green transition and energy efficiency of buildings in Denmark.

When fully implemented, the hub would be an improved basis for an automatic generation of recommendations in EPCs that could be linked with the building stock targets in long-term renovation plans.

It could also be beneficial to link the hub and the national building renovations plans (in EPBD recast) with local strategic climate energy plans (SECAPs), which also targets the 2050 goal of CO₂ neutrality. Climate and energy plans are in place for all municipalities in Denmark based on the C40 methodology (DK2020 initiative). The monitoring and implementation of these plans could be linked to BRPs, which in principle will target the 2050 plans for climate neutral buildings.

Greece

In Greece, energy audits, as defined in the context of this questionnaire, are integrated in the EPC scheme, with the EPC being the end result of the audit. The engineer (energy expert) issuing the EPC has to visit the building or building unit, collect all relevant data, perform the necessary calculations and upload the data to the EPC registry. A reference software for the calculations is provided by the Technical Chamber of Greece, while commercial software packages with a more user-friendly interface and integrated with other engineering software are also available.

Similarly, recommendations for improving the energy efficiency (consultancy) are mandatory as a part of the audit leading to the EPC.

In addition to GDPR issues, the following aspects need to be considered in the future:

- Legislation is required to define the rights of the building owner to the energy audit data as opposed to the intellectual property rights of the energy expert (also politically sensitive issue).
- Technical implementation is required to ensure that each user only has access to the data they need and to make data anonymous where necessary. Particular care should be taken with buildings with unique characteristics that can be easily identified even if the data is anonymised (e.g. a big hotel that is unique in a postal code).
- Organisation unit (e.g. in the Department of Energy) is needed for coordinating the various data collectors.

Malta

In Malta, EPCs are registered directly by the Building and Construction Authority (BCA), which is a good step towards digitalising information on buildings. However, a public database is not yet available. As for audits, digital summary templates (Excel files) are submitted for non-SMEs, but there is no platform which aggregates all submitted data, so the data has to be processed manually by EWA.

Malta launched several schemes to support building renovation and published its latest long-term renovation strategy in 2021, which includes several targets. However, there is no clear indication of the set-up of a building renovation roadmap.

Digital building logbooks have not yet been considered at national level.

The following barriers have been identified with respect to making data from energy audits available in Malta:

- Issues related to data protection, especially given the size of Malta. For example, in some sectors, there are only one or two major companies and thus publishing data might provide insights into sensitive information that the companies do not wish to divulge.
- Lack of an online system where energy auditors can upload their results, which can then be easily aggregated and analysed by the authorities
- Lack of agreement and communication between different ministries regarding the sharing of data and resources
- Lack of resources available within the respective departments to launch public databases

Poland

In Poland, the databases are residual and it is difficult to extract summarised information from them. The records are only checked manually. BRPs as well as the logbooks are mentioned in the Polish Long Term Renovation Strategy. Concrete measures must be taken to put the plans into practice.

To create a proper system in Poland, the following activities are necessary as a first step:

- Establish a database for audits
- Create an electronic template for energy audits
- Create legislation to make the reporting of audits mandatory

Slovenia

In Slovenia, the data of energy audits is not prepared in such a way that it can be easily stored in a database, on the other hand, an EPC was developed to be digitalised and actually is. The data is available in a PDF document. These EPCs are in the database, while more detailed data is stored in the software input file and is not transferred into the registry. In principle, data is accessible for a particular building, but not (easily) for the whole building stock.

Regarding BRPs, knowledge is available, projects on this topic and the communication with the ministry have been established. However, decisions need to be made and formal activities initiated.

In summer 2022, the Geodetic Administration of the Republic of Slovenia (GURS) completed the EU-funded e-Prostor project, which digitised real estate records and enabled e-commerce in the field of spatial planning and real estate management. Also, EPCs are accessible, but not the data coming from energy audits. Any further information regarding buildings, real-estate and infrastructure will be linked to this government cloud data. The legislation should also make the data from audits available.

In general, professionals are of the opinion that the audits should be more strongly integrated into EPCs and that at least preliminary information (short energy audits carried out during on-site visits) should be standardised and added to the EPC database. A voluntary form is available in the EPC registry in which independent experts can enter data on building elements, TBS, etc. However, as the inputs are voluntary, this approach has not been very successful. Opponents argue, that completing these forms takes too much time. Making this information available requires an obligation in the regulation and user-friendly input forms.

Spain

In Spain, some public entities (like EREN) are trying to advance on digitisation, but most municipalities lack the resources for such processes. However, they are trying to plan a digitisation process. For instance, Leon's municipality is planning to digitise all building conservation inspections (ITEs) in a public platform on which public agents and assessors can upload their documents.

It is noteworthy that there have been tools existing for the census and inspection of the state of conservation of buildings that are approaching the end of their estimated useful life. These tools make the inclusion of EECs (Energy Efficiency Certificates) in the reports on the state of conservation of buildings compulsory.

Likewise, for new buildings a Building Book is compulsory, which contains, among other things, the manual for the use and maintenance of the building in order to plan the correct use and conservation of the installations and construction elements. In addition, this tool is planned to be interactive, so that it must be updated by the owners as interventions are carried out in the building, whether or not they derive from construction faults.

As a new initiative, the Existing Building Book tool, which brings together all the tools described above, is being promoted throughout Spain. This document, which is currently fully subsidised by the regional governments and promoted by the technical rehabilitation offices, in addition to a complete inspection of a building's construction and energy performance, adds a second chapter to be developed by the assessors: the potential for improving the building's performance and the action plan for its renovation.

Thus, if this voluntary tool for owners becomes standard, Spanish public administrations will be able to map the complete state of the building stock and carry out a controlled development of the necessary interventions to reduce CO₂ emissions and improve health and living conditions, which are currently in disrepute in a large part of Spanish buildings. This boost and the establishment of the Existing Building Book tool will allow Spain to comply with its Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan Agenda.

3 Readiness of next-generation EPC schemes to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

3.1 Target of the analysis of next-generation EPC schemes

The content of an activity in crossCert was to see the extent to which the proposals for next-generation EPCs meet the requirements for linking them to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs.

3.2 Basic features and use of logbooks and BRPs

Logbooks and BRPs are instruments for monitoring individual buildings and especially energy renovations of buildings or a building stock. There are some aspects to be considered when setting up and using logbooks and BRPs:

3.2.1 Logbooks

Data and information capture:

- Capture of basic information about the building, such as construction year, type, size and usage
- Record of energy consumption data to understand current energy needs

Energy assessment:

- Integration of data on the building envelope, heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems, lighting and other relevant systems
- Evaluation of the building's energy performance, SRI, comfort indicators, potential energy savings and CO₂ emissions

Historical data:

- Record of renovations and modernisations performed
- Documentation of maintenance activities and repairs

Recommendations and measures:

- Provision of recommendations for energy efficiency measures based on the assessment
- Specification of priorities and estimated costs for implementation

Regular updates:

- Scheduling regular updates to capture changes in the building's condition or implemented measures
- Integration of monitoring systems for continuous energy consumption tracking

3.2.2 Building Renovation Passports

Holistic approach:

- Involvement of various disciplines such as architecture, engineering, energy consulting and environmental protection
- Consideration of life cycle costs and environmental impacts

Energy and environmental goals:

- Setting energy and environmental goals for the renovation

- Integration of renewable energies and sustainable technologies

Detailed documentation:

- Comprehensive recording of all relevant information about the building and renovation measures carried out
- Documentation of materials, technologies and renovation methods

Monitoring and evaluation:

- Establishment of monitoring systems to track the performance and efficiency of implemented measures
- Regular assessment of goal achievement and potential adjustment of the renovation strategy

Interactive use:

- Creation of a tool that can be used by various stakeholders, including building owners, authorities and energy consultants
- Integration of digital platforms for ease of use and updates

Both instruments should be tailored to specific requirements and contexts and should be accepted by relevant stakeholders, including building owners, construction experts and authorities.

3.2.3 Technical requirements for next-generation tools

The technical integration of new energy certification approaches with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs roadmaps requires a systematic process to ensure data consistency, interoperability and efficiency. In order to gain an insight into the technical background of such tools, the following issues must be considered:

API integration: The implementation of robust Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) is necessary to enable seamless data exchange between energy consulting platforms, logbook systems, renovation roadmaps and energy certificate generators. This facilitates the integration of current and accurate information from various sources.

Data standardisation: Utilising standardised data formats and protocols ensures a consistent representation of energy consumption data, renovation plans and other relevant information. This simplifies the integration and exchange of data between different systems.

Bidirectional data flows: Incorporating bidirectional data flows allows for the direct influence of updated information from logbooks, renovation roadmaps, or energy consultations on the energy certificate. Similarly, changes in energy certificates should be reflected back in logbooks and renovation plans.

Automated updating: The integration of automated processes for updating energy certificates based on input from energy consultations and implemented renovation measures ensures a timely and accurate reflection of building efficiency.

Blockchain technology: Considering the use of blockchain technology can enhance data integrity and confidentiality. Blockchain can also be utilised to establish a transparent and immutable history of renovation measures and certification information.

Machine learning for analysis and forecasting: Implementing machine learning algorithms for comprehensive data analysis and forecasting future energy efficiency based on planned renovation measures facilitates preventive planning and targeted interventions.

Cybersecurity measures: Implementing stringent cybersecurity measures is crucial to safeguard the security of transmitted data, particularly when handling sensitive information regarding energy consultations, renovation plans and building efficiency.

Cloud-based infrastructure: Leveraging cloud infrastructures for data storage and processing provides a scalable and accessible environment for data exchange and linking various systems.

Interfaces for stakeholders: Developing user-friendly interfaces for all stakeholders, including energy consultants, building owners and certification authorities, fosters acceptance and facilitates collaboration.

Interoperable software architecture: Creating an interoperable software architecture enables smooth integration of energy certificates, energy consulting platforms, logbooks and BRPs, leading to an efficient and cohesive environment for managing building efficiency data.

The technical integration of these measures requires careful planning and implementation to ensure that the different elements work seamlessly together and effectively contribute to advancing renovations and optimising building energy efficiency.

Depending on the tools, which are introduced in the following pages, different aspects of the above requirements have been successfully applied and are recommended when developing tools or interfaces between databases.

3.3 Next-generation EPC schemes of various crossCert sister projects

H2020 projects have developed several tools to enhance renovation measures and to capture and monitor the building stock, its documents like EPCs and renovation activities.

This report analyses the following tools in terms of their readiness to be linked:

- Logbooks
- Building renovation passports
- Tools to support energy audits
- Concept for the use of data from energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

SRI, IEQ, training modules, guidelines for logbooks and BRPs and developing networks were not part of the task.

The following chapter explains the available tools, the output of specific tools, the area of application, the data input and the origin of data, the availability of technical information and the interoperability.

According to the requirements of the EPBD and thus the requirements for linking EPCs, energy audits, logbooks and BRPs, the aspects to be fulfilled by the different next-generation EPC tools were defined and the tools themselves were rated for the following practical aspects:

- Interoperability
- Adaptability to national conditions
- Availability of technical information
- Value provided to the end user
- User-friendliness (understandability, accessibility via a digital interface, etc.)
- Overall readiness to be linked

The figures created for each tool show the rating of the respective tool from 1 to 4, where 1 is a less good rating and 4 is a good rating.

Within this task, tools from 13 H2020 projects and other projects were screened in detail. The following tools were chosen for evaluation on the basis of their type, progress and completeness:

- ALDREN – BRP
- D²EPC platform
- EDYCE platform
- iBRoad-Log and iBRoad-Plan
- iBRoad2EPC

EUB-SuperHUB, ePanacea and the EPC RECAST platform were not available at the time of preparing this report.

The report at hand provides a short description of each of the selected tools. In the crossCert report D2.7 Cross testing data (results) from the second generation of new EPCs a detailed description of most the tools and several others can be found.

3.3.1 ALDREN - BRP

3.3.1.1 Description of the tool

"The ALDREN Building Renovation Passport (BRP) is a dynamic instrument to be used and updated over time along the renovation path to deep renovation. It includes a 'LogBook' where comprehensive collected data better informs building owners and managers about the current technical energy, Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), and financial performance status of their building and a tailored Renovation Roadmap or 'RenoMap' with one or multiple steps to reach high energy performance in the medium to long term.

The BRP is a useful and dynamic instrument to increase data accessibility and to create more transparency along the whole renovation path with big data interoperability.

The ALDREN BRP is flexible and modularity structured based on 8 modules correlated but also independent by each other. It has been developed in two versions to facilitate the use and the data comprehension: a digital version comprehensive of all data collected, calculated, or evaluated during the ALDREN BRP preparation and a paper version which could provide both core and overall indicators according to the reader (owner or public authorities or auditor)."²

3.3.1.2 Output of the tool

"The ALDREN BuildLog

The ALDREN BuildLog has been structured into 6 modules with specific and respective protocols to follow for their fulfillment independent from one to another but at the same time, they could share data, in order to optimize the information collection process. The BuildLog could facilitate access to structured information about how the building was originally designed, what changes have been made and what is its actual performance service level and planned maintenance.

The ALDREN RenoMap

The ALDREN RenoMap allows the building owners to plan long term strategies for the renovation of their building following the ambitious energy performance requirement toward 2050 NZEB buildings objectives. It aims at reaching different objectives, both related to the coming project and the building lifetime:

- *Providing a complete overview of the NZEB compliant elementary renovation actions (ERAs) which could be implemented on the building;*
- *Setting and evaluating a complete building renovation potential considering the application of all ERAs;*
- *Identifying primary packages of renovation actions to implement in the initiated project, considering components degradation, owner's priorities, return on investment, energy performance and technical interactions;*
- *Setting a long-term plan and organizing the renovation packages according to technical requirements and opportunities (tenants replacement...);*
- *Evaluating performance indicators of the potential intermediate renovated states to provide the building owner the information to shape the initiated renovation project by integrating more or less renovation packages."³*

² <https://aldren.eu/building-renovation-passport>

³ <https://aldren.eu/building-renovation-passport>

In the digital version of the ALDREN BRP, the following ALDREN BuildLog modules (1 to 6) are integrated, according to the specific calculation protocols developed in the project:⁴

Module 1: Building picture –building information like general information, geometry, building physics and building services

Module 2: Energy rating & target – a consistent, harmonised, unique European energy performance rating, based on ISO/CEN standards, offering comparability and transparency across the EU to provide common metrics and highlight the quality of financial instruments related to renovation.

Module 3: Energy verification – a framework for energy performance verification that allows actual (measured) performance to be compared with simulated (predicted) performance. It encompasses a “Design for Performance” protocol that sets out and tracks the actions required during the deep renovation process. It also includes a “Performance Verification Tool” (PVT) to compare predicted and actual performance at different levels of granularity.

Module 4: Comfort & well-being – a protocol for assessing health and well-being. It is based on an index called ALDREN-TAIL to rate the Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ) of buildings undergoing deep renovation, focusing on four key components: thermal environment (T), acoustic environment (A), indoor air quality (I), luminous environment (L). TAIL ratings can and should be evaluated before and after the renovation.

Module 5: Cost value risk – a protocol for evaluating the impact of energy and non-energy benefits associated with deep renovation on the financial value and risks of office and hotel buildings.

Module 6: Documentation BIM – general indicators related to the existing materials for different issues to check the availability and format of all information.

Module 7 (elementary renovation actions) and Module 8 (NZEB Roadmap) are elements of the ALDREN RenoMap.

3.3.1.3 Area of application

The ALDREN BRP is applicable to non-residential buildings – in particular for offices and hotels.

3.3.1.4 Data input and origin of data

The data comes from simulations, detailed building inspections, documents and measurements based on best practice and the consistent use of CEN and ISO standards and is fed into an Excel document.

3.3.1.5 Availability of technical information

Technical information on the measurements and calculation methods is available on the ALDREN project website.

3.3.1.6 Interoperability

At the moment, data is manually fed into the ALDREN BuildLog by experts who have received specialised training. It could also be automatically fed into the ALDREN BuildLog through an automated connection to existing databases and various other sources (EPC database, BMS, BSO, or others) already identified. Integrating the BIM LoD by dedicated user interfaces (not realised within the ALDREN project) could be a further implementation after the end of the project.⁵

The project has developed protocols for each of the modules. They can be integrated into existing EPC schemes and software. Interoperability therefore depends on the EPC software used in the country or region concerned.

⁴ Salvalai, G., D2.6 – ALDREN Methodology note on rendering of the collected data and results in a building renovation passport, Italy 2019, p. 74

⁵ Salvalai, G., D2.6 – ALDREN Methodology note on rendering of the collected data and results in a building renovation passport, Italy 2019, p. 75

3.3.1.7 Readiness of the ALDREN BRP to be linked to energy audits and EPCs

Figure 11: Readiness of the ALDREN BRP to be linked to energy audits and EPCs

The overall readiness for linking is rated 1. This is because all the modules are linked to each other, but there is currently no linkage to other databases (e.g. EPC databases), to other sources of building information (e.g. the cadastre) or to BIM. As stated in the D2.6 – ALDREN Methodology note on rendering the collected data and results in a building renovation passport, information could also be automatically fed into the ALDREN BuildLog through an automated connection to existing databases and various other sources, which has not been realised within ALDREN, but the technical basis is foreseen.

Therefore, the special attention to the linkage is rated 2, as the ALDREN BRP combines BRPs and logbooks, but the connection to EPCs or databases is not included at the moment.

As the ALDREN BRP is a tool based on Excel, it can be adapted to national circumstances, although it is intended to serve as a harmonised tool based on CEN and ISO standards.

The availability of technical information is rated 4, as all necessary information is available on the project website.

The value for the end user is rated 3, as the tool contains a lot of information, which should be in a building logbook, but it is not possible to integrate existing EPCs or audit reports.

The user-friendliness is rated 2, as it is designed as a multi-sheet Excel, which is not very attractive to the user. A web tool with infographics and a user-friendly presentation of the data would be advisable.

3.3.1.8 Recommendations

“A consistent, harmonized, unique European energy performance rating, based on ISO/CEN standards, offering comparability and transparency across the EU to provide a common metrics and highlight the quality for financial instruments connected with renovation. A rating scale with classes from A-G has been defined to compare and identify in priority the buildings fitting best for deep renovation and to evaluate the impact of renovation actions on energy performance.”⁶

The harmonisation requests would be met by applying the developed modules, as they are based on CEN and ISO standards. Nevertheless, national adaptations will have to be made in order to meet the national legal requirements.

⁶ <https://aldren.eu/energy-rating>

3.3.2 D²EPC platform

3.3.2.1 Description of the tool

The D²EPC platform enables the calculation of an EPC based on BIM (Building Information Modelling) and a digital twin, integrating the smart readiness level of buildings, human comfort related and financial indicators and environmental aspects. Techniques for the correct geolocation of EPCs can be applied both in an automated/semi-automated manner and with a manual user-defined position via a smartphone application/handheld GNSS antenna. The dynamic nature of EPC geovisualisation provides a spatiotemporal element that is crucial for understanding the multiple factors that interact and affect the overall energy performance of a building.

The D²EPC BIM-based Digital Twin enables the unification of various forms of user-provided data with dynamic information, while the WebGIS tool enables various options for analysing and visualising the available data. The unified D²EPC Web platform will host the display of all the results from the various components and sub-components, such as the EPCs, the KPIs and the additional services. Through the web platform, the user will be able to adjust and configure certain components, as well as to directly request the ad hoc execution of certain processes.⁷

The proposed D²EPC scheme is expected to transform EPCs into a user-friendly, reliable and cost-effective information tool for both the general public (building users, occupants, building owners, property managers, municipalities, public authorities, etc.) and professionals (building managers, engineers, designers, etc.), as well as to provide the basis for transforming EPCs registries into consistent policy-feeding mechanisms.

The D²EPC is a comprehensive tool, considering the linkage to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs and using many new indicators for an operational EPC.

3.3.2.2 Output of the tool

The output of the tool is an EPC based on asset rating and real energy consumption (operational rating) and a WebGIS tool for policy makers to benchmark buildings at different levels.

3.3.2.3 Area of application

The D²EPC platform can be used for any type of building at any stage of planning or construction.

3.3.2.4 Data input and origin of data

“The building’s documentation can be divided into four (4) main categories. The first category is an information set enclosing the general description of the building, while the second depicts its division into thermal zones according to the operational characteristics of each space. The last two categories include the analytical descriptions of the elements that comprise the building’s envelope and the installed technical systems, respectively. All the information at the four categories can be derived either from its BIM model, or the auditor can insert them manually through the D²EPC Web Platform. The resulted set of the building’s data.”⁸

Data on human comfort (CO₂ concentration, humidity, temperature, indoor air quality) and energy and water consumption come from sensors and meters. The SRI is calculated according to the D²EPC methodology. Financial parameters for the calculation of future consumption costs are entered individually by the EPC issuer. To quantify the building’s overall comfort performance, various environmental parameters are utilised together with the respective boundaries of proper building operation per parameter. The approach is based on the personalised comfort profiling engine, which

⁷ Cano Cabañero, A. et al, D²EPC Manual v1 – Next-generation Dynamic Digital EPCs for Enhanced Quality and User Awareness, Spain, 2022, p. 6

⁸ Cano Cabañero, A. et al, D²EPC Manual v2 – Next-generation Dynamic Digital EPCs for Enhanced Quality and User Awareness, Spain, 2023, p. 19

contains a machine-learning clustering algorithm capable of identifying patterns and trends in previous user data to infer the occupant's preferred limits.

3.3.2.5 Availability of technical information

All data is available to the user, who must register to use the platform. A manual with detailed instructions on how to use the platform and enter the necessary data is also available on the website.

3.3.2.6 Interoperability

The D²EPC platform uses JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) as its data exchange format. JSON allows data structures from any language to be transferred into formats that are recognised by other languages and platforms.

Another format used is CSV (Comma-separated values). It is used to merge large amounts of data that are not directly connected to each other. It is frequently used between different databases. When using this format, the structure must be precisely synchronised between the parties.

The WebGIS tool uses a GIS cloud server implemented with the OGC Geoserver, an open-source server for sharing geospatial data and the PostgreSQL database in combination with the PostGIS extension for managing spatial information.

The D²EPC platform is a prototype, which was developed to show what a dynamic EPC concept could look like. In order to be able to use this tool on a broader basis, future developments are necessary and planned.

3.3.2.7 Readiness of the D²EPC platform to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

Figure 12: Readiness of the D²EPC platform to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and building renovation passports

The overall readiness of the D²EPC platform to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs is not far advanced and there is also no special attention to it at the moment. As the tool is a prototype and further developments are planned, it is expected that this feature will be improved. Storage of past EPCs or building plans and monitoring of renovation measures are not foreseen. EPCs from different stages of a building can be downloaded as PDFs and stored locally or on any cloud service.

The theoretical interoperability is rated 4, as widespread programming languages and data exchange formats are used.

As the tool uses calculation methodologies based on CEN and ISO standards, adaptations to national circumstances are necessary and also technically possible.

On the D²EPC website, numerous documents explain the D²EPC and the WebGIS tools in detail and guide the user through their use.

User-friendliness is rated 2 because the data input currently has to meet strict technical requirements and users need further training to use the tool properly.

3.3.2.8 Recommendations

In EU Member States where asset rating is the main certification method, D²EPC can be used as an additional tool to provide information to the building owner and user and to deliver measured and metered data as required by the EPBD. The field of application will be mainly large buildings with a high level of automation and monitoring. In any case, the user will need the skills to understand what is presented on the platform, how to operate it and how it can be interpreted in order to make adjustments if necessary.

The availability and specific technical requirements of the monitoring devices and connectivity to the platform are necessary to use the tool, but its use could be costly if monitoring devices or smart tools must be installed in a building. If the monitoring devices become state of the art, the use of the platform could be widespread.

Furthermore, data protection issues need to be solved and training for EPC issuers will be beneficial.

3.3.3 E-DYCE platform

3.3.3.1 Description of the tool

E-DYCE (Energy flexible DYNAMIC building CErtification) is the natural evolution of conventional EPC into real time optimisation of building performance and comfort by capturing the building's dynamic behaviour and at the same time providing transparent feedback through an intuitive interface. It complements the current EPC labelling method and does not compete with it.⁹

The E-DYCE concept is aimed at extending the capabilities of building energy professionals towards their customers and providing useful information to the tenants, which can potentially include push notifications on real-time operational suggestions and/or recommendations for planning and renovation according to specific profiles.¹⁰

It is a software feature (EnergyPlus) that can be implemented in existing software programs.

The tool refers specifically to energy audits and existing data. These should first be processed in a monitoring plan and then on a modular simulation platform.

EPC issuers are the ones who feed the tool. EPC consultants, end users and property managers are the defined target group who will use the tool.

The E-DYCE platform consists of¹¹:

- Sensors, a data acquisition system and communication protocols. The purpose of these elements is to gather data on various variables, including heat and electricity supply, heating and hot water supply and return temperatures, as well as comfort and air quality data such as indoor temperature, relative humidity and CO₂ concentration.
- A platform to manage the simulation processes, input/output data and data storage. This platform is called Fusix.
- The PREDYCE (Python semi-Realtime Energy DYNAMics and Climate Evaluation) library, which allows parallel and automatic runs of EnergyPlus simulations and processing of the results. It is the technical core of the E-DYCE simulation platform and one of the main contributions of the E-DYCE project.

⁹ <https://edyce.eu/>

¹⁰ Larsen, O. K. et al. , E-DYCE_2.4_Protocol_18.02.22_Final, Denmark, 2022, p. 13

¹¹ 1st E-DYCE webinar: Data collection and processing for Dynamic Energy Performance Certification <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=90NuNFbp1AM&t=5149s>

3.3.3.2 Output of the tool

The following functions are the output of the tool¹²:

- Provide a methodology for dynamic certification of buildings based on openly available resources and tools for technology and service providers, effectively creating an evolving, technology neutral ecosystem.
- Generate substantial savings of 30 kWh/m² (+ 1 energy class) in buildings certified through a dynamic scheme, therefore benefiting the owner, the tenant and the service provider, and thus incentivising all three.
- Leverage the savings generated and reinvest them in energy efficient refurbishment and optimisation, scaling up the number of certified buildings to a level that can provide policy makers with meaningful data.

3.3.3.3 Area of application

E-DYCE complies with the current Energy Performance Building Directive (EPBD) and the definition of nearly Zero Energy Buildings (nZEB) and can be applied to any building of any typology, location or level of intelligence and will generate substantial savings of one energy class by guiding the user to unlock the potential of free running operation.¹³

3.3.3.4 Data input and origin of data

The platform integrates energy simulations, free operation of buildings, energy demand forecasting, micro-generation management (i.e. energy storage and consumption, etc.).

The tool requires building geometry (IDF file), weather data (in EPW format) and a JSON file containing all user requests such as KPIs to be computed, parameters to be modified and runtime as input. Furthermore, building physics and details about building service systems are needed.

Input data from existing sources (CAD, BIM cadastre or other sources) is supplemented by an inspection process.¹⁴

E-DYCE will be open to a large set of potential input data, including the possibility to use existing building related resources and collect and process additional specific data. The data available in the EU Member States and beyond Europe is not homogeneous and large variances have been considered, especially for data not included in EPC data exchange formats, i.e. XML. Hence, the processing stage of the E-DYCE data collection needs to be adaptable, smart and efficient, allowing to collect and adapt data from heterogeneous sources. Existing EPC data will also be implemented.¹⁵

3.3.3.5 Availability of technical information

Technical information about the tool is available on the project website.

3.3.3.6 Interoperability

PREDYCE is based on three main modules, which are designed to work together, but can also be used independently:

- The EnergyPlus input data file editor allows to act on the building model both on the building structure and the activities. The IDF editor module contains a collection of methods to modify EnergyPlus building models for different purposes. Such models are handled using the EnergyPlus scripting language.
- The runner module allows the automatic management of a batch of multiple parallel simulations. It is a script including a Python class that can be instantiated and used by a user or by other

¹² Chiesa, G., E-DYCE_D1.2_Operational_dynamic_EPC_specifications_18.12.2020_Final, Italy 2020, p. 5

¹³ Junak, K., D 3.3 Analysis of new scales and KPIs, Poland, 2024, p. 15

¹⁴ Chiesa, G., E-DYCE_D1.2_Operational_dynamic_EPC_specifications_18.12.2020_Final, Italy 2020, p. 62

¹⁵ Chiesa, G., E-DYCE_D1.2_Operational_dynamic_EPC_specifications_18.12.2020_Final, Italy 2020, p. 64

PREDYCE modules to perform multiple simulations and analyses at once. The runner is in charge of creating a pool of simulations that are then executed asynchronously by multiple instances of EnergyPlus on the same machine according to the number of cores of the current CPU (this can be specified by the user or automatically defined in the process). This pool of simulations can be a simple combination of all possible actions described by the user in the input JSON file.

- The KPIs calculator is able to perform calculations, analyses and graph plots by accessing EnergyPlus output files. Such actions can be performed automatically after each simulation, called by the runner module, or manually by a custom Python script. Analyses usually consist of resampling output data and applying formulas to compute indicators based on European standards. Some calculations may also include graphs, which can be saved in a subfolder structure to be associated with single simulations and visualised when needed.¹⁶

3.3.3.7 Readiness of E-DYCE to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

Figure 13: Readiness of E-DYCE to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

In terms of the overall readiness of E-DYCE to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs, there are still technical challenges with data input. Furthermore, linking the transfer of the results to other tools such as logbooks is not foreseen.

The theoretical interoperability is rated 3, as weather data, BIM files and consumption data can be implemented and Python and JSON are in use, which are common data formats and data exchange formats. As mentioned above, there are still challenges in this area.

Adaptations to meet national legal requirements are necessary and also possible through the methodology.

The E-DYCE website offers extensive information about the methodology, the tool and technical requirements.

The value for the user is rated 3, as there is valuable information output, such as current consumption and improvement measures to reduce energy consumption. There is no link to a logbook, which would be a further asset for the user.

¹⁶ Chiesa, G., E-DYCE_D3.1_Dynamic simulation platform_28.02.2022_Final - Energy flexible DYnamic building Certification, Italy 2020, p. 18 ff

3.3.3.8 Recommendations

An adaptation to national standards would be useful, as the certificate has to follow country specific standards and calculation methodologies.

For the end user, the tool is very user-friendly because it provides direct suggestions and results for optimising building performance and comfort.

3.3.4 Smart Energy Performance Assessment Platform - SEPAP

3.3.4.1 Description of the tool

The project ePanacea identified challenges in EPC schemes like the gap between the theoretical and actual consumption, the lack of a proper inclusion of smart and highly efficient technologies for zero-emission buildings, the lack of user awareness and the lack of convergence of EPC schemes across the EU member states.

To tackle the challenges, ePanacea has conducted a series of analyses on new features (e.g., SRI, IEQ) for the next generation of EPCs. Based on these analyses, ePanacea has developed a prototype called the Smart Energy Performance Assessment Platform (SEPAP). This platform utilises advanced techniques such as dynamic and automated simulation modelling, big data analysis, machine learning or inverse modelling. This platform is the primary outcome of this project. The platform provides three energy evaluation methods (M1, M2, and M3) that vary in complexity, from a basic assessment (M1) to an almost energy audit (M3).

3.3.4.2 Output of the tool

Assessment method 1 (M1): Smart & performance data-driven energy performance assessment:

The method used to determine energy consumption is relatively simple and relies on a combination of energy consumption data and inverse modelling techniques. Theoretical energy consumption values are calculated based on the building's geometry and physical parameters. These theoretical values are then fine-tuned using data from energy bills, HDD and CDD (if indoor temperature is available). With these inputs, the energy consumption data is decomposed, and the monthly energy data is generated as a result.

Assessment method 2 (M2): Simplified method based on monthly calculation (ISO 52016) interval and its calibration:

Assessment method 2 is based on the monthly method of ISO 52016, considering that smart technologies, artificial intelligence and machine learning for automated assessments as well as advanced models for occupation profiles are increasingly present in the buildings.

This method involves an initial calculation by the platform, which identifies energy uses that require calibration to align energy consumption with the measured values. The user or assessor then makes the final decision on the adjustments to be implemented.

The Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) can be calculated by entering the functionality level for various services (e.g., heating/cooling emission control, flexibility, grid interaction, etc.). The final and primary energy consumption is presented annually in kWh. In addition, energy indicators are provided by services, energy sectors and energy components on an annual basis while heating and cooling demands are on a monthly basis.

Assessment method 3: Advanced & automated simulation modelling based on hourly calculation (ISO 52017) and its calibration.

This is the most complex method based on the calibration of an advanced energy model (based on energyPlus). The approach implements a sequential structure that allows obtaining a calibrated model based on actual consumption patterns (i.e., EPC in use) at the same time that it will provide a more accurate standard EPC after correction by climate and use.

3.3.4.3 Area of application

The tool can be used for all types of buildings.

3.3.4.4 Data input and origin

General data, such as location, floor area, and construction type of the building are entered as input data. A list of weather data stations, and heating and cooling schedules are predefined, but the user can also edit if different data are available. Envelope data and data related to HVAC systems, as well as data related to lighting systems, other equipment (not included in the EPB service, such as washing machines), DHW and data from energy bills are also filled in by the user/assessor.

The assessment method 3 requires the use of various open-source tools, such as the OpenStudio SketchUp plug-in, the OpenStudio application, the PAT (Parametric Analysis Tool), and the OpenStudio Server.

3.3.4.5 Availability of the technical information

Information about the SEPAP is available at the project website. To ensure proper application of the tool further explanations and guidance is necessary.

3.3.4.6 Interoperability

The SEPAP platform from ePanacea uses a combination of different data exchange formats to ensure interoperability with other systems. The use of standardised formats such as JSON and XML forms an essential basis for this. These formats enable smooth communication and data exchange between different systems and applications by ensuring that data can be transferred in a structured and standardised way.

SEPAP also relies on RESTful APIs, which enable simple integration and communication via the internet. RESTful APIs are widely used and offer a flexible and scalable way of exchanging data between different platforms and integrating web services.

3.3.4.7 Readiness of SEPAP to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

Figure 14: Readiness of the SEPAP platform of ePanacea to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

Interoperability 2 because 3D -models can be implemented when using assessment method 3. But there is no possibility to import 3D models for assessment method 1 and 2. The values have to be filled in manually. Another aspect is the interoperability with other databases or tools. According to the use of standardised formats such as JSON and XML forms an essential basis for a linkage is given but interfaces are not yet programmed.

There is no special attention to the linkage to energy audits, BRPs or logbooks. Therefore this issue is rated with 0.

Technically the platform can be adapted to national circumstances and EPC schemes but in case of Austria or Poland for example, the ePanacea calculation methodology is very different and less detailed and there would be a very high effort necessary to adapt the tool to national conditions. But in this case it would be a different approach. Therefore the adaptability to national conditions is rated with 2.

The availability of technical information is rated with 3 as a lot of information can be found at the project website and videos, which explain the application of the SEPAP but there is still information needed on the data input of a variety of buildings and guidance on how to implement metered data for example.

The value provided to the end user in regard to the linkage of tools is rated with 2, as there are calculations for new indicators like the SRI or IEQ. On the other hand, data input is mainly done manually and there is no time-saving in data input. Furthermore, there is no functionality like the connection to other databases for the use of data.

The user-friendliness is rated with 2 as there is potential to improve the user interface and the logical order of the data input and changing walls or windows requires deleting and entering a new item. Furthermore some terms are not clear. Furthermore, there are a lot of menus and drop-down options, which could be designed in a way that the user only has to click only a few times to input data.

The overall readiness of the linkage is rated with 1 as there are linkages to weather data and partially to simulation platforms but not specifically to energy audits, logbooks or BRPs. These linkages are expandable.

3.3.4.8 Recommendations

During the third round of cross-testing several issues occurred – see inserting name of deliverable – . It is recommended to solve these issues to make the SEPAP useable on a broad basis.

In addition, creating an interface to import data from other sources, especially databases and to transfer the results and important information from the calculation to other databases or web services.

3.3.5 iBRoad-Log & iBRoad-Plan

3.3.5.1 Description of the tool

The Horizon 2020 iBRoad project has developed a model for an individual BRP, a customised long-term (5–30 years), step-by-step plan/roadmap for building renovation. It is complemented by a logbook – a digital building repository for information, such as building plans, works implemented, energy consumption and production, etc. The tools can be linked to the EPC in two directions:

- The logbook (iBRoad-Log) can integrate relevant data from the EPC in the context of a 'snapshot' recording the state of the building at a specific point in time and the renovation journey; the EPC itself can be uploaded as a document below the snapshot.
- The BRP (iBRoad-Plan) can extend or replace the building upgrade recommendations included in the EPC.¹⁷

3.3.5.2 Output of the tool

The output of the tool consists of:

- A comprehensive and detailed BPR, outlining measures in a specific order to avoid lock-ins, expected energy use, costs, energy class and other aspects

¹⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/754045/reporting>

- An online repository of building information including building envelope, energy demand and consumption, overall performance, etc.

iBRoad's Logbook "all in one place" approach is extremely useful for homeowners. It can also help technicians called in for home maintenance or improvements, as well as energy auditors and other service providers. iBRoad's Logbook organises the building's history in "snapshots", allowing owners to revisit each stage in their building's evolution.

Building owners can enter specific renovation measures that have been carried out in the logbook and thus document the renovation progress. They can align planned renovation measures with the iBRoad2EPC and check after completion whether the building is still on the target path.¹⁸

The iBRoad renovation passport (iBRoad-Plan) is developed by a trained energy auditor, following an on-site building assessment and an interview with the homeowner. The auditor uses the iBRoad software to present a step-by-step improvement plan, taking into account the homeowner's needs and preferences. The aim is to renovate the building in a suitable and future-proof way.

3.3.5.3 Area of application

The tool is intended to be used for existing single-family houses.

3.3.5.4 Data input and origin of data

The data is collected during an on-site visit by the energy auditor. This includes an interview with the homeowners, a checklist, the collection of building plans and other documentation, possibly some on-site measurements, and finally calculations using the national EPC software. Building plans and energy consumption and production can also be integrated.

The iBRoad Roadmap Assistant operates like a "wizard", guiding the issuer through the process of collecting and entering the data needed to issue the BRP (iBRoad Plan). The iBRoad-Log is a user-friendly front-end to the structured logbook database allowing all relevant data to be entered, updated and reviewed.

3.3.5.5 Availability of technical information

Several freely accessible reports on specific aspects of iBRoad are available on the project's website.

3.3.5.6 Interoperability

The programming languages used are JSON and PostgreSQL.

JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is a widely used data format that can be easily understood and processed by various programming languages. It is commonly used for data exchange between different systems because it is easy to read and write.

PostgreSQL is a relational database management system that offers powerful SQL syntax and advanced features for database queries and manipulation. It also supports JSON data types and provides functions for working with JSON data within the database. This allows JSON data to be stored, queried and manipulated directly within PostgreSQL, improving interoperability between JSON and the database.

Interoperability is therefore considered practicable.

¹⁸ Mellwig, P. et al., Technical report on the definition of the proposed concept, content and methodology of iBRoad2EPC, Germany, 2023, p. 10

3.3.5.7 Readiness of iBRoad-Log and iBRoad-Plan to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

Figure 134: Readiness of iBRoad-Log and iBRoad-Plan to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

The overall readiness of iBRoad-Log and iBRoad-Plan to be linked to energy audits and EPCs as well as the special attention to the linkage are rated 3, as it encompasses all features required in the EPBD – such as a building logbook, a BRP, the integration of consumption data and energy production and the connection to the EPC as well as the information capture by energy auditors.

An automatic transfer of data from the EPC software to the iBRoad tools would be much appreciated by testers.¹⁹

As national software is used for the EPC calculation, national legal requirements are already met. Therefore there is no assessment for the adaptability to national conditions. 4. Nevertheless, there are language issues, which could be easily solved and there may be other issues that might affect the integration of the iBRoad concept:

“The relevant legal structures of each country ought to be identified, while regulations and bureaucratic processes that hinder local implementation of the iBRoad concept must be investigated to determine how they can be adapted. This could involve the need and procedures for obtaining building permits in different countries. In Bulgaria, for example, it is not yet feasible to integrate iBRoad into national policies, as smaller buildings (iBRoad targets single-family houses) are not required to undergo an audit or possess EPCs. Legal structures must be further explored to see if they already consider a stepwise renovation and if incentives support this.”²⁰

The value provided to the end user is considered to be high, as the iBRoad tools mentioned above deliver a BRP, which can also be stored in the iBRoad logbook. Furthermore, other data and documents can be stored in the logbook.

“The web platform is clearly structured and iBRoad has been established in a non-technical language that the end users (homeowners) can fully understand it (simple and aimed at non-specialists).”²¹ Therefore the availability of technical information is rated with 4.

¹⁹ Werle, M. et al., The iBRoad field test experience – Bulgaria, Poland, Portugal, Germany, Germany 2019, p. 13

²⁰ Dorizas, P. V., How can Member States implement iBRoad? Barriers and drivers for countries willing to explore the feasibility and replicability of iBRoad, Brussels 2019, p. 11

²¹ Dorizas, P. V., How can Member States implement iBRoad? Barriers and drivers for countries willing to explore the feasibility and replicability of iBRoad, Brussels 2019, p. 14

The user-friendliness is rated with 2 as the testers of the tool had difficulties with the language and would prefer having the tool available in their national language. There is also a large amount of data input necessary and the design could be improved.

3.3.5.8 Recommendations

Adaptation to local requirements is necessary, as is the translation of data fields. However, this process has already been tested in another case and is quite straightforward to implement. Thereon, a short and specific training for professional auditors would be useful. While the iBRoad project focused on single-family houses, the tools and methods developed can be adapted to many other types of buildings.

The iBRoad project has tested its tools in Bulgaria, Poland, Portugal and (partially, only the logbook) Germany. The testing entailed adapting the tools to the countries' specifications, training professional auditors and implementing the process for producing the roadmaps and logbooks in suitable buildings. The work with 27 auditors and 65 buildings confirmed the tools' potential to support deep renovation, receiving positive feedback from both homeowners and professionals. iBRoad then collaborated with the Irish Green Building Council (IGBC), which organised a further test with 11 auditors and 20 more buildings, corroborating the potential.

The iBRoad tools were built with the potential to import relevant data from EPC databases and other related repositories; the connections were not developed as part of the iBRoad project, but it is advisable to do so.

3.3.6 iBRoad2EPC

3.3.6.1 Description of the tool

iBRoad2EPC integrates BRP features into existing EPC systems in six pilot countries (Bulgaria, Spain, Greece, Poland, Portugal and Romania). The aim was to bring existing EPCs closer to a decarbonisation roadmap and introduce a focus on the long-term goal of decarbonisation.

The output of iBRoad2EPC was created with an online tool called the iBRoad2EPC Assistant. The main objectives of this tool are:

- Create the iBRoad2EPC in a uniform design
- Output the iBRoad2EPC in an online version
- Create a printable page, that can be attached to the EPC and leads to the iBRoad2EPC
- Provide clear and intuitive user guidance
- Make it easier for issuers to assign renovation measures at specific times
- Output a clear selection of prefabricated content
- Allow issuers to easily overwrite all default texts
- P easy expandability with additional modules

Together with the Renovation Roadmap and the Logbook, the iBRoad2EPC forms the iBRoad product family. Various combinations of interconnecting the individual tools are conceivable.²²

3.3.6.2 Output of the tool

iBRoad2EPC can be an annex to the EPC as well as a stand-alone consulting product. The basic content, the general design and the key features, however, make the brand core of iBRoad2EPC and remain the same regardless of the flexible adjustments.²³

iBRoad2EPC comprises of a basic module (unified core) and additional modules. The unified core

²² Mellwig, P. et al., Technical report on the definition of the proposed concept, content and methodology of iBRoad2EPC, Germany, 2023, p. 9, 86

²³ Mellwig, P. et al., Technical report on the definition of the proposed concept, content and methodology of iBRoad2EPC, Germany, 2023, p. 13

features include the output of indispensable technical information (renovation advice) for building owners and, in addition, a unifying methodology and layout as well as a uniform software infrastructure.²⁴

In addition to the basic module, it is possible to add special features to the iBRoad2EPC individually. This will allow an upgrade of the iBRoad2EPC tailored for the specific needs of each country. When implementing iBRoad2EPC, countries can decide whether and which additional features they want to integrate, so that iBRoad2EPC fits in well with the existing consulting landscape or other existing policy instruments in the building sector. The additional features are the SRI Module, IEQ Module, Energy Demand Module, Investment cost Module or other modules as required.²⁵

3.3.6.3 Area of application

The tool (web service) can be applied to all building types. It was especially created to be applied to existing buildings.

3.3.6.4 Data input and origin of data²⁶

Typical project input data that issuers need to provide is building information that allows the building to be classified according to country, address, environment, climate zone, year of construction or type. This data is crucial to filter appropriate and individual renovation recommendations. These recommendations should also include EPC information, the tenure status, renovation triggers, EPC addressees, and recommendation addressees. With these specifications, further text can be customised and recommendations can be adjusted. For each renovation step and improvement measure, the issuer will calculate the impacts of the measures, cost and energy savings, CO₂ emissions and energy class, according to specific national EPC calculation methods and outside of the tool. All this data is used as input to iBRoad2EPC.

The data is gathered as part of an obligatory on-site visit by an EPC auditor. Several data sources are combined in iBRoad2EPC:

- Issuer selection from predefined data sets in the iBRoad2EPC databases for each implementing country [image / icon database, measures database, measure specification database, notes database, text database, MEPS / regulations database with country specific information from long term renovation strategies (target U-values, preferred energy sources, differentiation between building types)]
- Links with existing EPC systems/tools to provide automatic input of data
- Issuer customisable data such as technical measure descriptions

The iBRoad2EPC Assistant is a backend tool that compiles and transmits data for a specific building on request. The request can be submitted from different platforms or frontends. This allows the iBRoad2EPC Assistant to be connected to various existing tools in the Member States, such as EPC software or energy performance registers. In addition, a standardised frontend for the Assistant is delivered to enable data entry independently from external software. The iBRoad2EPC Assistant uses a multi-faceted application programming interface (API). The data is stored in relational databases. This avoids the need of EPC schemes to sample each parameter separately, which would make the extraction of building data too labour intensive.

²⁴ Mellwig, P. et al., Technical report on the definition of the proposed concept, content and methodology of iBRoad2EPC, Germany, 2023, p. 7, 8

²⁵ Mellwig, P. et al., Technical report on the definition of the proposed concept, content and methodology of iBRoad2EPC, Germany, 2023, p. 18

²⁶ Mellwig, P. et al., Technical report on the definition of the proposed concept, content and methodology of iBRoad2EPC, Germany, 2023, p. 9, 56

3.3.6.5 Availability of technical information

Detailed information on technical specification of data formats is not yet publicly available (February 2024), but it can be made available upon request. The overall structures and connections can be viewed on the project’s website.

3.3.6.6 Interoperability

The programming languages used are JSON and PostgreSQL.

JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is a widely used data format that can be easily understood and processed by various programming languages. It is commonly used for data exchange between different systems because it is easy to read and write.

PostgreSQL is a relational database management system that offers powerful SQL syntax and advanced features for database queries and manipulation. It also supports JSON data types and provides functions for working with JSON data within the database. This allows JSON data to be stored, queried and manipulated data directly within PostgreSQL, improving interoperability between JSON and the database.

Interoperability is therefore considered practicable.

3.3.6.7 Readiness of iBRoad2EPC to be linked to EPCs and logbooks

Figure 15: Readiness of iBRoad2EPC to be linked to energy audits, logbooks and building renovation passports

The overall readiness for linking is rated 4, as the web tool is designed with the target to be linked to various other tools like EPC software programs or EPC registers. An iBRoad2EPC can also be stored in a national logbook.

The interoperability of the web tool is rated 4, as the programming languages and data exchange formats allow data exchange with other tools and linkages have already been tested and implemented in several countries. Furthermore, the links and necessary tools or modules can be integrated in the different countries as required. iBRoad2EPC was developed to be used independently if needed or to be deeply embedded in existing software via an API. The modular approach allows for its integration into different regional contexts. Hence, it is expected that this flexibility will allow for a wide adoption in different contexts and with different levels of “investment”.

The special attention to the linkage is rated 4, as the web tool designers focussed especially on this feature.

The adaptability to national conditions is rated 4, as the iBRoad2EPC can be linked to national or regional EPC software programs.

The value provided to the end users is rated 4, as they receive a very appealing, understandable and useful document, which can be linked to the EPC and the logbook, whereby users have all the information available they need to make decisions for renovation measures and to monitor their progress

"The user-friendliness is rated 4, as the visual language is clear, fresh and illustrative. It is meant to motivate and break down the inhibitions of users who are put off by the rather abstract and technical content. A pictogram of a house shows the measures for renovating the building envelope. It is designed to be universally valid and to symbolise all building types. All measures concerning the technical building equipment are represented by icons. Improvements to building components are shown by the respective icon changing colour from grey or white to green."²⁷

3.3.6.8 Recommendations

Based on already existing and extensive questionnaires from energy issuers, iBRoad2EPC can be rated as very user-friendly, as this was the feedback received by a large majority.

To ensure full customisation, the default database of the iBRoad2EPC renovation advice should be adapted to the national context and translated.

iBRoad2EPC has produced several supporting documents and contents for trainings alongside with training material for construction professionals.

²⁷ Mellwig, P. et al., Technical report on the definition of the proposed concept, content and methodology of iBRoad2EPC, Germany, 2023, 30

3.4 Utilising findings from sister projects

The findings from the crossCert sister projects, including X-tendo, U-CERT, iBRoad, ALDREN, D²EPC, and others, demonstrate the potential for an integrated and dynamic approach to energy performance assessment. These projects highlight key advancements that can support the seamless linkage of next-generation EPCs with energy audits, logbooks, and BRPs, thereby improving building data management and renovation planning.

Digitalization and interoperability

The integration of EPCs with logbooks and BRPs requires standardized data formats, interoperable software architectures, and APIs that allow seamless data exchange. Projects like iBRoad and ALDREN have developed structured digital tools that enable EPCs to store and track renovation progress, while D²EPC and E-DYCE leverage real-time data inputs to refine energy performance assessments. These advancements ensure that EPCs evolve from static labels into dynamic, regularly updated instruments that reflect the real-time performance of buildings.

Enhanced data exchange and automation

Several sister projects emphasize the need for automated data input and bidirectional data flows between EPCs, energy audits, and renovation roadmaps. The use of blockchain (as explored in ALDREN) and cloud-based infrastructure (as proposed in SEPAP) enhances data security and accessibility, fostering more accurate performance tracking and planning. Automated updating mechanisms, such as those found in iBRoad2EPC, ensure that EPCs remain relevant throughout the building's lifecycle.

Supporting informed renovation strategies

By linking EPCs with logbooks and BRPs, next-generation EPCs can serve as key instruments for informed decision-making. Tools like iBRoad-Plan and iBRoad2EPC provide structured renovation roadmaps, helping homeowners and building managers avoid lock-in effects while optimizing renovation investments. Additionally, methodologies developed within SEPAP and D²EPC enable EPCs to incorporate operational energy data, making them more reflective of actual building performance rather than relying solely on calculated ratings.

Standardization and policy alignment

Harmonization with national and EU-level requirements remains a crucial factor in ensuring widespread adoption of these integrated tools. Many of the sister projects align their methodologies with EPBD requirements, ISO/CEN standards, and national EPC frameworks, allowing easier implementation across Member States. However, as seen in ALDREN and E-DYCE, further adaptation to national conditions is necessary to accommodate legal and administrative differences.

User-centric approaches for wider adoption

For EPCs to be fully integrated with energy audits, logbooks, and BRPs, they must be accessible and user-friendly. iBRoad's approach of providing clear, structured, and intuitive user interfaces demonstrates how digital EPCs can engage homeowners and professionals alike. Similarly, iBRoad2EPC's modular design and adaptability to national EPC tools make it a valuable example of how user experience can be enhanced to encourage engagement with energy performance data.

Outlook

The integration of next-generation EPCs with energy audits, logbooks, and BRPs represents a fundamental shift towards a more data-driven, transparent, and actionable approach to energy performance assessment. The insights gained from the crossCert sister projects highlight different ways for developing interoperable, automated, and user-friendly tools that can support the EU's renovation wave and long-term decarbonization goals.

Future efforts should focus on further harmonization, enhanced data integration, and broader adoption to ensure that EPCs become a cornerstone of energy-efficient building management across Europe. Continued exchange between relevant stakeholders, along with the further advancement of technical solutions, can help ensure that EPCs play an increasingly central role in energy performance assessment and renovation planning.

4 Recommendations and guidelines

Besides technical challenges regarding data transfer from one tool to another, there are organisational challenges for the use of next-generation EPC tools, logbooks and BRPs. Such challenges are the low digitalisation level, isolated schemes/lack of linkage of available data (e.g. databases, software tools), data protection issues, lack of willingness to link different sources of information, low trust and low interest in EPCs.

The findings from the crossCert sister projects, including X-tendo, U-CERT, iBRoad, ALDREN, D²EPC, and others, demonstrate the transformative potential of integrating next-generation EPCs with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs. By leveraging digitalization and ensuring interoperability, these projects offer innovative solutions that enable the seamless exchange of building performance data, supporting more efficient renovation planning and management. Standardized data formats, interoperable software architectures, and real-time data inputs enhance the accuracy and relevance of EPCs, transforming them from static labels into dynamic, up-to-date instruments that reflect real-time performance.

Additionally, automated data flows and blockchain technologies further enhance data security, accessibility, and transparency, which is essential for informed decision-making in renovation strategies. The integration of EPCs with tools like logbooks and BRPs, along with user-centric approaches and alignment with EU and national policies, is key to ensuring broader adoption and facilitating a smoother transition toward more sustainable and energy-efficient buildings. These advancements underscore the importance of a collaborative, data-driven approach in achieving long-term decarbonization and renovation goals across Europe.

Therefore, the consortium elaborated a set of recommendations and guidelines on how to drive the implementation of next-generation EPCs, logbooks, BRPs and the linkage to energy audits. The valuable insights from the sister project's tools (see 3.4 Utilising findings from sister projects) have been carefully integrated into the recommendations and organized into clear, coherent groups with a purposeful structure.

4.1 Overcoming organisational and digitalisation barriers

To effectively overcome organisational and digitalisation barriers, the following key strategies are essential:

Enhancing digitalisation: Encourage the adoption of digital tools by showcasing their benefits to energy auditors, EPC assessors, and building owners. Provide training and user-friendly platforms to facilitate adoption.

Stakeholder engagement: Foster cooperation by bringing stakeholders together, presenting the benefits of integration, and addressing objections through dialogue and incentives.

Developing dynamic EPCs: Transition from static EPCs to dynamic energy certificates that are continuously updated with real-time data from energy audits, smart meters, and renovation logbooks.

4.2 Strengthening the link between EPCs, energy audits, logbooks, and BRPs

To create a cohesive and efficient system for building energy renovation, the following steps should be taken:

Verification and regular updates: Encourage periodic energy audits to update EPC data, ensuring that certificates reflect the current energy performance of buildings. Providing subsidies or incentives for energy audits can help increase their uptake.

Integration of energy consultation data: Utilize insights from energy audits and consultations to refine EPCs, logbooks, and BRPs, making them more comprehensive and actionable.

Identifying and filling gaps: Conduct regional assessments to identify missing elements in national or local renovation strategies and select suitable tools from existing projects to enhance current frameworks.

Strategic data selection: Ensure that only relevant and high-quality data is used in EPCs and related tools to balance the benefits of data integration with the complexity of managing large datasets.

Policy and regulatory integration: Leverage upcoming updates to guidelines, standards, and laws to embed next-generation EPCs, new indicators, BRPs, and logbooks into regulatory frameworks.

4.3 Creating a supportive framework for data sharing and renovation incentives

To create a supportive framework for data sharing and renovation incentives, the following strategies should be implemented:

Establishing data sharing mechanisms: Develop frameworks and secure data-sharing protocols that facilitate the exchange of building performance data while maintaining privacy and security.

Continuous monitoring and updates: Implement mechanisms that enable the regular tracking of energy consumption and automatic updates of EPCs based on renovation activities and real-time performance data.

Mandatory renovation reporting: Introduce obligations for reporting renovation measures, possibly requiring the use of standardized digital tools for data submission.

Targeted renovation planning: Promote tools that generate customized renovation roadmaps, ensuring recommendations are tailored to specific buildings and owner priorities.

Financial incentives for renovation measures: Link subsidies and financial incentives to the implementation of renovation measures validated through EPCs, energy audits, and BRPs.

4.4 Improving user experience and market acceptance

To improve user experience and market acceptance, the following approaches are crucial:

Simplified user processes: Ensure that digital tools used for EPCs, logbooks, and BRPs offer a smooth, automated, and user-friendly experience with minimal complexity.

Increasing end-user interest: Change the perception of EPCs from an administrative burden to a valuable tool by improving communication strategies and highlighting their benefits for property value, energy savings, and comfort improvements.

Training and awareness campaigns: Conduct outreach and educational initiatives for homeowners, tenants, energy auditors, and real estate professionals to enhance engagement and understanding of next-generation EPC tools.

The successful integration of these approaches requires close collaboration between energy consultants, property owners, authorities and other relevant stakeholders. Through seamless integration, these tools can contribute to making renovations more effective and improving the long-term energy efficiency of buildings.

4.5 Technical considerations for effective integration

The technical integration of new energy certification systems with energy consultations, logbooks and BRPs requires a systematic approach to ensure data consistency, interoperability and efficiency. It is recommended to adhere to the following recommendations when developing or linking tools:

API integration: Implement robust APIs to facilitate seamless data exchange between various digital tools and databases.

Data standardisation: Use common data formats and protocols to ensure compatibility across systems.

Bidirectional data flows: Allow dynamic updates between EPCs, energy audits, and renovation records, ensuring continuous data exchange.

Automated updating: Enable real-time updates of EPCs based on implemented renovation measures and monitoring data.

Blockchain technology: Explore blockchain applications to enhance data security, transparency, and integrity.

Machine learning for analysis and forecasting: Utilize AI-driven analytics to predict energy performance improvements and recommend renovation actions.

Cybersecurity measures: Implement strong data protection strategies to ensure compliance with privacy regulations and secure sensitive building data.

Cloud-based infrastructure: Leverage cloud solutions for scalable and accessible data storage and integration.

Stakeholder interfaces: Develop intuitive user interfaces for all relevant stakeholders, ensuring ease of access and interaction.

Interoperable software architecture: Design software platforms that allow smooth integration of EPCs, energy consulting tools, and renovation databases.

4.6 The role of the recommendations in promoting building energy renovation

The outlined recommendations play a crucial role in accelerating building energy renovation by addressing both technical and organisational barriers. Here's how they contribute to the promotion of energy renovation:

Providing accurate and actionable information: By integrating real-time updates, energy audits, and consultation data into EPCs and logbooks, building owners receive accurate and detailed insights on their renovation needs, enabling better decision-making.

Enhancing financial feasibility: Linking financial incentives and subsidies to renovation measures validated through EPCs and BRPs motivates property owners to invest in energy efficiency improvements.

Facilitating compliance and policy alignment: Ensuring that EPC frameworks align with national and EU policies supports the broader goal of achieving climate neutrality and increased energy efficiency.

Encouraging stakeholder collaboration: Improved cooperation among auditors, policymakers, and building owners leads to a more cohesive and supportive renovation ecosystem.

Increasing public awareness and engagement: By making EPCs more user-friendly and highlighting their benefits, public interest and participation in energy renovations will grow.

Streamlining renovation processes: Digitalisation, automation, and improved data-sharing mechanisms reduce bureaucratic hurdles, making the renovation process more efficient and less time-consuming.

The technical integration of these approaches requires careful planning and implementation to ensure that the different elements work seamlessly together and effectively contribute to advancing renovations and optimising building energy efficiency.

By implementing the developed recommendations and guidelines, the integration of next-generation EPCs with energy audits, logbooks, and BRPs can be significantly improved. A well-connected and digitalized system will enhance the effectiveness of building renovations, contribute to energy efficiency goals, and promote a more sustainable built environment. Close collaboration among policymakers, energy professionals, and building owners will be essential to ensuring these tools are widely adopted and effectively utilized.

5 Conclusions

Readiness of nex-generation EPCs to be linked with energy audits, logbooks and BRPs

The linkage of next-generation EPCs with energy audits, logbooks, and BRPs marks a significant transition toward a more data-centric, transparent, and practical method of assessing energy performance. Findings from the crossCert sister projects illustrate various approaches to creating interoperable, automated, and user-friendly tools that can drive the EU's renovation efforts and contribute to long-term decarbonization objectives.

Initiatives such as iBRoad and ALDREN have introduced well-structured digital solutions that allow EPCs to document and monitor renovation progress, while D²EPC and E-DYCE utilize real-time data to enhance the accuracy of energy performance evaluations. These innovations transform EPCs from static certificates into dynamic, continuously updated tools that provide a real-time snapshot of a building's energy efficiency.

The tools evaluated feature good interoperability and high adaptability to national circumstances and legal frameworks. Technical information is mostly available on the project websites. Not all the tools evaluated, pay special attention to linking, but basically they are all technically designed to be linked to other information sources and tools. Therefore, the overall readiness to be linked to next-generation tools was rated as good for almost all the evaluated tools.

The value provided to the end user and the user-friendliness vary, mainly depending on the tool's design (web application with appealing infographics is rated higher than simple Excel tools or methodologies) and technical functionality. Some tools are very sensitive when it comes to data exchange and data formats and thus the applicability is limited.

The pathway to successful linkages and promotion of building energy renovation

There is a clear imperative for building performance assessment tools to evolve towards greater integration with external databases such as energy performance certificate (EPC) databases, building information modeling (BIM), energy audit databases, geo information systems, building logbooks, BRPs, smart meters, sensors and other relevant sources.

This integration is essential for ensuring comprehensive data availability and facilitating a holistic approach to building performance assessment and renovation planning. Moreover, transitioning from spreadsheet-based tools to web-based platforms with intuitive interfaces and visual representations holds promise for enhancing user experience and accessibility. By incorporating infographics and user-friendly data presentations, these tools can become more engaging and accessible to end users.

Additionally, ensuring interoperability with national standards and legal requirements while maintaining adaptability to different contexts is crucial. Utilizing common programming languages and data exchange formats can facilitate seamless data exchange and integration with other tools and databases, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of these assessment tools.

Finally, providing comprehensive support in the form of training materials and assistance for users, including EPC issuers and construction professionals, is essential for widespread adoption and utilization. Addressing data protection concerns is also paramount to foster trust and confidence among users regarding data privacy and security.

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